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Ciências
ULisboa

**A Dynamical System Approach to Uni and Multi-Variate Weather
Analysis over Portuguese Territory**

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Mestrado em Física e Astrofísica

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I am very grateful for all the support I received from my tutor, Professor Ana Nunes, as well as from Professor Carlos DaCamara. Sílvia A. Nunes was also a reliable contributor to this work.

Grateful to my parents for their constant support in my choices, be it for learning the arts of circus or learning the arts of physics.

Abstract

Keywords: dynamical systems, extremes, data science, weather.

The main objective of this work is to investigate and reproduce some of the existing research in the analysis of weather dynamics with an approach based on dynamical system. Most studies of climate extremes rely on statistical approaches or machine learning, but chaotic dynamics can provide a deeper understanding of atmospheric behavior. The method can easily be extended to multivariate systems. The general observation that the atmosphere displays chaotic dynamics leads us to numerical analysis of some chaotic attractors. The Lorenz attractor is used extensively in this study. We use these systems to see how much information can be obtained from the time series of a few metrics derived from a discrete trajectory in phase space. This trajectory must be long enough to represent the system globally, meaning that it must be longer than the characteristic time of the system. After probing with numerically integrated systems, we transpose the acquired knowledge to practical applications of real data over Portuguese territory, from 1979 to 2020. We search for the physical meaning behind each metric and investigate if they can provide a better understanding of weather extremes and compound events. Practical applications are explored by crossing the data with registered wildfire activity in the same period of time.

We mainly focus on temperature and wind speed and assessment is made of their role in major wildfires. According to their dynamical signatures, warm-windy compound extremes fall into two different classes, one with a more predictable character, and the other less predictable.

Resumo

Palavras chave: sistemas dinâmicos, extremos, ciência de dados, clima.

O estudo da dinâmica atmosférica a partir de dados observacionais tem sido abordado na literatura recente do ponto de vista de métricas assentes na teoria dos sistemas dinâmicos. O principal objetivo deste trabalho é apresentar essa abordagem e aplicá-la a uma série de 42 anos de dados diários de temperatura e velocidade do vento no território continental português. Tradicionalmente, a maioria dos estudos sobre extremos climáticos têm-se baseado fortemente em métodos estatísticos clássicos ou em (*machine learning*). Esses métodos são eficazes para analisar grandes volumes de dados e para realizar previsões a curto ou médio prazo. No entanto, por vezes estes métodos têm dificuldade em capturar a complexidade inerente dos sistemas não lineares e caóticos como a atmosfera terrestre. A hipótese que fundamenta este tipo de metodologia é que as variáveis atmosféricas — como temperatura, humidade e velocidade do vento — evoluem de acordo com leis determinísticas não lineares que, quando representadas no seu respetivo espaço de fases, podem revelar padrões e estruturas que escapam a abordagens convencionais. Um aspeto inovador deste estudo é a tentativa de classificar eventos extremos compostos segundo a sua assinatura dinâmica.

O capítulo 1 dedica-se à introdução dos conceitos e da metodologia. É introduzido o conceito de trajetória no espaço de fases, a partir da qual se obtém a dimensão local, assim como o *Extremal Index*, que são parâmetros fundamentais da metodologia utilizada.

O capítulo 2 dedica-se à análise de atratores numericamente integrados. Utilizamos o atrator de Lorenz e Baker's map para investigar até que ponto é possível extrair informações sobre as dinâmicas a partir de séries temporais reais, que resultam de algoritmos aplicados localmente no espaço de fases (a cada passo de tempo), e que consideramos ser as métricas do sistema. Depois de analisar o método de forma a perceber o significado físico por trás de cada métrica, o objetivo é entender se essas métricas — como dimensão, densidade e tempo de passagem, acoplamento - podem refletir propriedades relevantes e coerentes sobre a dinâmica subjacente do sistema. Para isso, simulamos trajetórias numéricas suficientemente longas no espaço de fases, assegurando que o tempo de integração seja muito superior ao tempo característico do sistema, o que garante que a trajetória seja representativa da totalidade do atrator, ou seja, que se aproxime da condição ergódica. Estudamos a sensibilidade das métricas a variações nos parâmetros de integração e introduzimos também uma nova métrica, R , que representa a densidade no espaço de fases.

Uma vez adquirida familiaridade com as ferramentas e o significado físico das métricas em sistemas dinâmicos numericamente integrados, passamos ao capítulo 3, onde aplicamos o conhecimento adquirido a dados reais, provenientes de observações meteorológicas no território português entre 1979 e 2020. Damos especial atenção à temperatura e à velocidade do vento, duas variáveis com influência direta nos riscos de incêndios florestais, um dos impactos climáticos mais devastadores e frequentes no território nacional. Discutimos a parametrização da análise assim como as correlações de anomalias,

numa primeira fase, em sistemas de uma só variável, e logo em sistemas bivariados, com a introdução de mais uma métrica que descreve o acoplamento, α , entre as variáveis. A análise inclui a investigação de correlações entre anomalias meteorológicas e anomalias das métricas. De facto verifica-se que as anomalias tendem a estar correlacionadas em certas alturas do ano, e anticorrelacionadas em outras. Esta observação é utilizada para dividir o ano em duas temporadas, uma temporada fria, de 4 meses de duração, e a temporada quente, de 8 meses de duração.

O capítulo 4 dedica-se à análise de extremos compostos de vento forte e temperatura elevada, e temperatura elevada e baixa humidade. Investigamos a relação existente entre dias de extremos compostos e a sua assinatura dinâmica. Investigamos se períodos de elevado ou baixo acoplamento entre a velocidade do vento e a temperatura podem estar correlacionados com extremos compostos de alta temperatura e fortes ventos. Agrupamos os eventos observados em duas grandes categorias: aqueles que apresentam características de previsibilidade no espaço de fases, com sinais de aproximação a regiões estáveis do atrator, que revelam padrões bem definidos, de configurações que tendem a repetir-se, e aqueles que ocorrem em regiões instáveis, cujas configurações não se repetem, e que apresentam características que os tornam mais incertos. Esta distinção é importante não apenas do ponto de vista científico, mas também operacional. Eventos com maior previsibilidade dinâmica podem ser utilizados para alertas precoces, enquanto os menos previsíveis exigem estratégias mais robustas de mitigação. Avaliamos também a estabilidade e robustez das métricas aplicadas ao mesmo território mas com diferentes resoluções espaciais.

Finalmente, no capítulo 5 cruzamos a informação obtida da assinatura dinâmica com os eventos identificados como sendo dias de forte atividade de incêndios florestais em Portugal, no mesmo intervalo de tempo. Procuramos, assim, estabelecer uma possível relação entre a dinâmica atmosférica captada por estas métricas e os dias de grandes incêndios, avaliando se existe coerência temporal entre os dias com assinatura dinâmica extrema e os dias com ocorrência de incêndios. Verificamos que as métricas permitem classificar os principais dias com ocorrência de incêndios em dias que tiveram maior influência do vento, e dias que tiveram menor influência do vento.

Os resultados preliminares sugerem que há, de facto, uma correspondência significativa entre certos tipos de comportamento dinâmico associados a extremos compostos e a ocorrência de incêndios. O acoplamento entre ventos e temperaturas, por exemplo, parece ser reduzido nos dias em que os maiores incêndios foram registados no período em consideração, como por exemplo, os incêndios de 2 de Agosto de 2003 e 15 de Outubro de 2017. Embora estes resultados ainda careçam de investigação mais extensiva, apontam para o potencial desta abordagem como uma ferramenta complementar aos modelos estatísticos e de previsão existentes.

Uma das vantagens desta abordagem é a facilidade com que pode ser estendida a sistemas com múltiplas variáveis. Em vez de tratar cada variável isoladamente, como ocorre frequentemente em análises estatísticas tradicionais, a análise assente em sistemas dinâmicos permite estudar a evolução conjunta de mais de uma variável, perdendo, para isso, informação detalhada sobre as dinâmicas locais em troca de uma visão global ampliada, captando possíveis interações não triviais entre as variáveis. Isso é particularmente relevante no contexto de extremos compostos, que são eventos extremos que ocorrem simultaneamente em múltiplas variáveis. Esses eventos são de difícil previsão e têm ganho atenção crescente na literatura científica e em políticas de mitigação de riscos.

A abordagem com base nos sistemas dinâmicos aos extremos compostos tem sido aplicada, nos últimos anos, por Faranda e coautores, a casos como os extremos compostos de humidade e temperatura (altos e baixos), pressão e temperatura (altos e baixos), e extremos frio-húmido-ventoso e húmido-ventoso. Neste artigo, damos atenção a um par de observáveis diferente, nomeadamente os extremos compostos de alta temperatura e forte vento. Para além da sua relevância como indicadores de extremos mete-

orológicos, os máximos quente-ventoso estão associados a incêndios florestais catastróficos na região mediterrânica, em particular em Portugal. Os grandes episódios de incêndios em Portugal estão quase sempre associados a condições atmosféricas dominadas por ventos fortes e secos, que favorecem o desenvolvimento e a propagação rápida de ignições.

Em conclusão, este trabalho procura demonstrar a utilidade de ferramentas de sistemas dinâmicos na análise de dados atmosféricos reais, com foco em eventos extremos. Para além de aprofundar o entendimento teórico das dinâmicas envolvidas, o estudo visa contribuir com novas ferramentas e perspectivas para o estudo de extremos climáticos, e para a compreensão dos fatores que os tornam mais ou menos previsíveis. Acreditamos que a integração destas abordagens com métodos clássicos pode oferecer uma visão mais completa dos riscos climáticos atuais e futuros, especialmente em regiões vulneráveis como Portugal.

Contents

List of Figures	viii
List of Tables	xiv
List of Abbreviations	xv
1 Introduction: notation and definitions	1
1.1 Trajectory in phase space	2
1.2 About dimension	3
1.3 About the extremal index	6
2 Analysis through numerically integrated attractors	9
2.1 Univariate analysis and Lorenz attractor	10
2.1.1 Graphical exploration	10
2.1.2 An approximation of the rotation around the fixed points through the metrics . .	14
2.1.3 Robustness of θ and d , introducing R	15
2.2 Bivariate systems and Baker's map	19
3 Data based analysis	23
3.1 Wind and temperature univariate system	24
3.1.1 Fine tuning the quantile	24
3.1.2 Declustering on real data	27
3.1.3 Anomalies and their relations	29
3.2 Wind and temperature bivariate data analysis	37
3.2.1 Co-recurrence ratio, α	37
3.2.2 Relation of anomalies	38
4 Compound extremes and bivariate metrics	43
4.1 Warm-dry compound extremes	44
4.2 Warm-windy compound extremes	52
4.2.1 Local approach to warm-windy compound extremes	52
4.2.2 Global approach to warm-windy CEs	59
4.2.3 Discussion	63
4.3 Modeling through DS metrics	65
4.3.1 Trend of α vs temperature	68
4.4 Coarsening the lattice	68

CONTENTS

5	From extreme events to DS metrics	70
5.1	Metrics signature	71
5.2	From analogs to metrics	74
A	Different definitions of dimension	79
B	Rescaling the lattice and reducing dimensionality	82
C	Variability of the metrics over the years	87
D	Extremes of α	89
E	Extra plots	90
	Bibliography	96

List of Figures

1.1	In red and blue the plot shows two numerical solutions of the Lorenz equations differing only in initial condition: one has $x_0 = -1.08$ and the other has $x_0 = -1.07$. After a thousand timestep of $\tau = 0.01$ integrated with Runge-Kutta 4 (RK4), trajectories end up in opposite 'wings'.	2
1.2	On the left, uniform distribution of points on a disk, and local dimension taken at its center, with $q = 0$. On the right, same radial coordinates as on the left but with isotropic distribution, and local dimension taken at its center. d is equal for both and is close to 2, corresponding to the dimension where the radial distribution is uniform (in this case, the disk).	6
1.3	On the left, uniformly distributed points in a 3D-sphere. On the right, same radial distribution, with a uniform angular distribution in a 2D space. d is the local dimension of the central point, provided by the algorithm.	6
1.4	The linear fit gives 1.005 for blue ($q = 0.95$), 1.03 for red ($q = 0.9$), and 1.05 for yellow ($q = 0.85$). All for Runge-Kutta integration with $\tau = 0.1$ and $T = 1000$.	8
2.1	On top, local dimension d , and at the bottom, local extremal index θ	10
2.2	ball B , with colors corresponding to logarithmic return values of exceedances. Points in yellow correspond to the center where values of $g_\xi(\vec{x})$ are highest.	11
2.3	Normalized histogram of $\eta(\vec{x}_i) = g(\vec{x}_i) - \mu$, for $g(\vec{x}_i) - \mu > 0$, compared with probability density function (2.2) in red.	12
2.4	Normalized histogram of $\eta(\vec{x}) = g(\vec{x}) - \mu$, for $g(\vec{x}) - \mu > 0$ of clustered and declustered exceedances, compared with probability density function (2.2) in red. On top-right declustering is done by picking a random point out of each cluster; on bottom-left, by taking the maximum value of η from each cluster; on bottom-right by taking the average value of η from each cluster.	12
2.5	Each column corresponds to a different point on the attractor. On the top row are depicted the points in ball B , with their respective value of $-\log(dist)$; in the middle row are normalized histograms of the occurrences for each η , compared to the exponential pdf; and at the bottom row are time series of the exceedances that occurred for $i \in [2 \cdot 10^4, 2.5 \cdot 10^4]$.	13
2.6	76 timesteps with $\tau = 0.01$ of the Lorenz attractor (2.1) around fixed point C (2.3) in red. Color bar corresponds to values of θ .	14

LIST OF FIGURES

2.7 1000 timesteps of a trajectory on the Lorenz attractor, integrated with RK4 with $\tau = 0.01$. There are three fixed points, at the origin and at the center of the 'wings'. Arrows show the direction in which the system evolves, and red lines are the eigenvectors of the fixed point at the origin. 15

2.8 Two examples of ball B and their respective logarithmic returns. Both have the same quantile (same number of points in B), very similar velocities, thus supposedly similar persistencies, but have different mean cluster size, thus different θ 16

2.9 R and θ seem to have their peaks inversely proportional to each others but with a phase difference of about 30 time steps. The dominant frequency of the orbit on the attractor is of 1.32 cycles per unit time, a period of 0.76. 16

2.10 On top, local θ at five different randomly selected points, as a function of the length of trajectory T . In the middle, d , and at the bottom, *radius* of the same five points. All with $\tau = 0.01$ and $q = 0.98$ 17

2.11 On top, local θ at five different randomly selected points, as a function of timesteps τ . In the middle, d , and at the bottom, *radius*, of the same five points as a function of τ . θ clearly depends on the timestep, which suggests careful selection of τ for any analysis. All calculations were made with $T = 10000$ and $q = 0.98$ 18

2.12 Red corresponds to a point at juncture of the 'wings' of the strange attractor; yellow to a point at the margin of the attractor; blue somewhere in the middle of one of the wings. θ takes an abrupt slope as q gets close to 1, but d has a different behavior. d is a more stable parameter. On the other hand, *radius* goes to zero, as we would expect. Yellow point shows a slight transition in d around $q = 0.9$, probably related to the distribution of points in ball B on the edges of the attractor, where ball B includes a region of phase space that is not part of the attractor. 18

2.13 The quantity $R\theta$ shows less dependence on the quantile. 19

2.14 10^4 iterations of system (2.4). 20

2.15 10^4 iterations of (2.4), metrics obtained for $q = 0.9$ 21

3.1 Metrics computed with the 98th quantile for 10 years of wind magnitudes, from 01/2014 to 12/2023. We observe some discretization of θ and a significant change in the last 3 years, from 2020 to 2023. The data from 2020 on, accidentally came from a different dataset that hasn't been through re-analysis. 25

3.2 Distribution of exceedances compared to the exponential pdf, for $q = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9$. Best fit should sit between 0.8 and 0.9. 26

3.3 10 years of wind magnitudes, from january 2014 to december 2023. θ versus d . $q = 0.85$. 27

3.4 Declustering effect on real data, wind magnitude on the upper half, and temperature on the lower half, both for point $i = 380$ 28

3.5 Metrics for 42 years of temperatures, from january 1979 to december 2020, for $q = 0.96$. Only first 10 years of time series were plotted for better visibility. We see seasonality playing an important role in the periodicity of the time series, maximas of d corresponding to winter. θ has two cycles per year. 29

3.6 On top: years 1979, 1995, 2010 of anomalies of temperatures (3.1). At the bottom: relative standard deviation (3.3). 31

3.7 Sign concordance of anomalies of temperatures with anomalies of d (on top), and with anomalies of θ (at the bottom). 32

LIST OF FIGURES

3.8	Mean sign concordance as a function of the start of semester 1. Semester 2 starts 6 months later.	33
3.10	For the wind, we find that sign concordance of anomalies of $(W, R\theta)$ are much stronger than (W, θ)	33
3.9	Duration of each season and respective sign concordance score, maximized for each year. Anomalies of d and T on top, and θ and T at the bottom.	34
3.11	Variance of wind, d_{wind} and $R\theta_{wind}$ anomalies, scaled to standard deviation 1. The relation between wind and $R\theta$ is still visible in variance.	35
3.12	On top, sign concordance, per season, without threshold, and at the bottom with threshold of $\sigma/2 = 0.5$	36
3.13	Distances of exceedances inside ball B for points $\xi = 10153$ (on top) and $\xi = 2045$ (at the bottom) for univariate and bivariate analysis. Distances of temperature correspond to the x -axis, and the ones of wind magnitudes to the y -axis. Red marks highlight the points common to both B_T and B_W . Bivariate exceedances are in black, and the ratio of the red marked points over the total bivariate exceedances is α	38
3.14	First 4000 days of the bivariate analysis of winds and temperatures (1979-1990).	39
3.15	In blue are the means for each day of the year with their respective standard deviation in black, computed by means of (3.4).	40
3.16	We see anomalies of α , d_{co} and $R\theta_{co}$ for years 1979, 1995 and 2010, computed with (3.1). There seems to be mostly negative sign concordance between α, d_{co} and $\alpha, R\theta_{co}$	40
3.17	Annual cycles of daily sign concordance of anomalies of the metrics, for each day of the year (equation (3.6)).	41
3.18	Sign concordance per year for $(\Delta'_\alpha, \Delta'_d)$ and per season/season, from 01/05 to 15/10, for $(\Delta'_\alpha, \Delta'_{R\theta})$. Negative anomalies dominate the positive ones.	42
4.1	Annual cycles of sign concordance of anomalies of the metrics, for each day of the year (equation (3.6)).	44
4.2	On top, the threshold at each gridpoint, corresponding to quantile 90th and 10th of the warm seasons of temperature and relative humidity, respectively. At the bottom, the resulting number of compound extremes per gridpoint, out of 705 univariate extremes of low relative humidity and high temperature.	46
4.3	Normalized distributions of the metrics on CEDs and warm seasons, estimated using a normal kernel smoother.	47
4.4	On top, α versus d_{co} of 7056 days of warm seasons, at the bottom, proportion of gridpoints with compound extremes, for each day of the warm seasons, ordered with their values of α	48
4.5	Values of α , θ_{co} , R_{co} , and d_{co} and fraction of CEDs that fall in each decile of the ranked time series of the warm seasons.	49
4.6	Geospatial distribution of compound extremes on CEDs with α values smaller and greater than 90th percentile of the warm season days.	49
4.7	Geospatial distribution of compound extremes on CEDs with d_{co} values smaller and bigger than the 10th percentile of the warm season days.	50
4.8	Mean anomalies (4.1) on CEDs, and on days that have $\alpha > P90$ and $\theta_{co} < P10$ (colormap scales are different for each map).	51
4.9	Distribution of CEDs and of days with DEs throughout the year.	52

LIST OF FIGURES

4.10	Sign concordance of anomalies of the metrics, for each day of the year.	53
4.11	Geographical distribution of thresholds and warm-windy compound extremes, from a total of 705 univariate extremes of temperature and wind magnitudes per gridpoint.	53
4.12	Ratio of warm-windy compound extremes in each 10th of the warm seasons, with their respective values.	54
4.13	Geospatial distribution of warm-windy compound extremes on CEDs with α values smaller than the 10th percentile and bigger than the 90th percentile of the warm season days.	54
4.14	Geographical distribution of thresholds and the resulting CEs per gridpoint.	56
4.15	Fraction of gridpoints with CEs: on top, fractions ordered by increasing value of α , at the bottom, distribution of days with fraction greater than 20% over the years.	57
4.16	Values of α , θ_{co} , R_{co} , d_{co} and $R\theta$ and fraction of CEDs that fall in each decile of the ranked time series, restricted to the warm season days.	57
4.17	Probability distribution function of the co-metrics over the warm season days, compared with the one of the 188 local CEDs, estimated using a normal kernel smoother.	58
4.18	Splitting of CEDs into 2 categories using k-means: unpredictable class in blue, and predictable class in green.	59
4.19	Geographical distribution of local CEs on CED_u and CED_p and respective number of occurrences (colorbar). It is worth noting that the colorbar for CED_u goes to 15, while it goes to 20 for CED_p	59
4.20	Probability distribution function of the co-metrics over the total period, compared with the one of the 162 CEDs, estimated using a normal kernel smoother.	60
4.21	Values of α , θ_{co} , R_{co} , d_{co} and $R\theta$ and fraction of CEDs that fall in each decile of the ranked time series.	61
4.22	Distribution of d_{co} values for CEDs with $\alpha > 3rd\ quantile$ and those with $\alpha < 1st\ quantile$	62
4.23	CEDs in the metrics space, divided in two categories using k-means.	62
4.24	Geographical distribution of global CEs on CED_u and CED_p and respective number of occurrences (colorbar). It is worth noting that the colorbar for CED_u goes to 12, while it goes to 20 for CED_p	62
4.25	Number of accounted CEDs in the neighborhood of days of extremes of α , as a function of the days difference.	63
4.26	Geographical distribution of clusters of CEs covering more than 20% of gridpoints over Portugal. Maps with clusters for two consecutive days show the distribution for the first (second) day in red (blue).	64
4.27	Number of CEDs per month, for both the local approach (in blue) and the global approach (in red).	65
4.28	On top, model for warm-dry CEs using local CEs, and at the bottom using the global CEs, both with warm season days only. Local model shows better performance.	66
4.29	On the left, model for warm-windy CEs using local CEs, and on the right using the global CEs, both with warm season days only.	67
4.30	Map of linear regression of averaged α as a function of averaged temperatures (averages over the seasons), over regions of $30km \times 45km$	68
4.31	Relative differences between the original α and the coarsened α_{coarse}	69

LIST OF FIGURES

5.1	20 most intense days in burned area by wildfires, with 15/10/2017 and 02/08/2003 ranking first and second, respectively.	70
5.2	Values of the co-metrics for 15/10/2017 and 02/08/2003, with the corresponding α in 4th and 15th place, respectively. For α only the yellow circle is visible because it covers the red circle, which is on the same spot.	71
5.3	Values of α in October 2017.	72
5.4	The 60 DIW with more than 10000 hectares of burned area over Portugal, and their respective bivariate metric values: temperature-wind on the left, temperature-humidity on the right.	73
5.5	The 60 DIW in parameter space. The 20 top DIW are highlighted in red.	74
5.6	Average wind magnitude (left panel), and average relative humidity (right panel) for each of the 60 DIW, as stratified into 2 clusters.	74
5.7	Maps of temperature (top row) and wind speed (bottom row) values for 15/10/2017 (left panels), for 40 analog means(central panel) and for the respective differences (right panel). Green pixels represent statistically non-significant differences.	75
5.8	Monthly distribution of analogs.	76
5.9	Values of the metrics and fraction of analogs that fall into each decile of the ranked time series.	77
5.10	Map of the 10 analogs of the 15/10/2017 and significant differences.	77
5.11	Monthly distribution of the 10 analogs and respective metrics signature.	78
A.1	Packing, Hausdorff, and box-counting methods from left to right respectively. Image by Prokofiev - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0, https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=12112582	80
B.1	The 4×3 lattice gets off track more often than the others. R is replaced by $R' = R/\bar{R}$ to make it independent of dimensionality. The same Figure for winds can be found in Extra Plots, Figure B.2.	83
B.2	The 4×3 lattice gets off track more often than the others but looks like it still is a good representation of the dynamics. R is replaced by $R' = \frac{R}{\bar{R}}$	84
B.3	Mean over the 42 years of each metric, for each lattice size.	84
B.4	Anomalies of d for different lattices of temperature over the same area, for years 1979, 2003 and 2015.	85
B.5	Sign concordance of anomalies (T, θ) for each lattice size. They are barely affected.	86
C.1	Yearly means of d , θ and R by (C.1), the dotted lines correspond to $\bar{x}_n \pm \sigma_n$ of year n . We see the increase of temperature, reflecting the global warming, with an increase of $1.5 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ over the 42 years. The other quantities do not exhibit major trends.	88
D.1	Yellow circles highlight the 10 smallest values of α and their respective signatures, whereas red circles highlight the 10 biggest values of α and respective signatures.	89
E.1	Plot of the trajectory with respect to d , θ and radius, R , of ball B . Color bar corresponds to the respective timestep i	90
E.2	42 years of wind magnitudes, from January 1979 to December 2020, for $q = 0.96$. Only first 10 years of time series were plotted for better visibility. We observe much less seasonality than for temperatures 3.5.	91

LIST OF FIGURES

E.3 Maximized sign concordance for temperature with season 1 from 15/03-13/09, and season 2 from 14/09-14/03. 92

E.4 Results for fixed 6 month seasons of sign concordance as a function of start of season 1. d and θ have opposite phases. It doesn't really make sense to split the year in seasons of positively and negatively related anomalies for wind magnitudes. Figure E.5 suggests the same. 92

E.5 Sign concordance with varying season duration. On top, we can say that sign concordance of anomalies (W, d) is not divided in seasons, with only a few exceptions, like in 1988. Anomalies of d always evolve in opposition to those of W . At the bottom, sign concordance of anomalies divided in seasons (W, θ) still holds, with a big variability of season duration, no clear pattern emerges. 93

E.6 On top, yearly sign concordance of anomalies of (W, d) and $(W, R\theta)$. At the bottom, same thing with threshold excluding anomalies which absolute value smaller than $\sigma/2 = 0.5$ 94

List of Tables

4.1	Comparison of the metrics' distributions: the 7056 days against the corresponding ones of the 1584 CEDs.	47
4.2	Comparison of the metrics' distributions: the 7056 days of the warm season against the corresponding ones of the 188 CEDs. μ_0 is the population mean, \bar{x}_{CED} is the sample of CEDs mean, and $\hat{\sigma}$ is the estimated standard deviation.	58
4.3	Comparison of the metrics' distributions: the 15341 days against the corresponding ones of the 162 CEDs. μ_0 is the full 42-year mean, \bar{x}_{CED} is the sample of CEDs mean, and $\hat{\sigma}$ is the estimated standard deviation.	60
4.4	Ranking of feature importance by MRMR algorithm, on the prediction of local and global CEs.	67
5.1	40 analogs of 15/10/2017.	76
E.1	Temperature: start of seasons 1 and 2 for each year and each metric d and θ	95

List of Abbreviations

DS - dynamical system

EI - extremal index

EVL - extreme value laws

RK4 - Runge-Kutta 4

PCA - principal component analysis

CE - compound extreme

CED - compound extreme day

DE - dynamical extreme

MRMR - minimum redundancy maximum relevance

DIW - day of intense wildfire

Chapter 1

Introduction: notation and definitions

We are interested in analyzing climate phenomenology based on the knowledge built around dynamical systems (DS), through the works initiated by Lorenz in 1963 suggesting that the atmosphere has the characteristics of a system with a strange attractor.

Our goal is to give continuity to the work previously done by [Faranda et al., 2017] and [Faranda et al., 2020], exploring and testing the potential of such a method, understanding the physical meaning of the metrics of local dimension and local extremal index in this context (described in next sections 1.2 and 1.3), and discovering what new features and advantages they could bring when compared to traditional statistical approaches. We will start with analytic examples, for both univariate and bivariate systems, and follow with real data analysis.

This first chapter is dedicated to the description of the methodology we used throughout the study.

1. INTRODUCTION: NOTATION AND DEFINITIONS

1.1 Trajectory in phase space

We project our analysis on an N dimensional phase space, where in the case of the data based analysis each dimension corresponds to a measure of some observable made at a specific geospatial point. The point in phase space at a specific time, t , corresponding to the ensemble of the N measurements, is $\vec{x}(t) = (a_1(t), \dots, a_N(t))$. This point will evolve in time and draw a trajectory in the N dimensional space. By discretizing time, we reduce the trajectory to a set of points, all computed with the same time interval $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^+$, where $\vec{x}(t_{i+1}) = \vec{x}(t_i + \tau)$, $\{i \in \mathbb{N} : 0 < i\tau \leq T\}$, and $T = i_{max}\tau$ is the total running time. The ensemble of measurements at a given timestep, i , for the geospatial area being studied, will correspond to a specific configuration which can be fully described by a single point \vec{x}_i in phase space. When setting ourselves at a given timestep, i , of the trajectory we will refer to \vec{x}_i as ξ .

Our hypothesis is that the atmospheric observables we will study have a chaotic attractor. In fact the Lorenz attractor, named after the mathematician Edward Lorenz, was detected in a model for air convection of the atmosphere. Non-linear systems often display chaotic characteristics, associated to aperiodicity and fractal dimension in their long term behavior. These chaotic attractors are characterized by their sensitivity to initial conditions that result in long-term unpredictability in spite of their deterministic nature. As illustrated in Figure 1.1, slight change in initial condition rapidly originates two totally different trajectories.

Our favourite example to illustrate through numerical integration such chaotic behavior throughout this work is the Lorenz attractor [Lorenz, 1991], described in the following chapter.

Figure 1.1: In red and blue the plot shows two numerical solutions of the Lorenz equations differing only in initial condition: one has $x_0 = -1.08$ and the other has $x_0 = -1.07$. After a thousand timestep of $\tau = 0.01$ integrated with Runge-Kutta 4 (RK4), trajectories end up in opposite 'wings'.

Considering that the atmosphere is also highly non-linear and aperiodic, with too many degrees of freedom to consider, we will use the time series of atmospheric data and assume that they correspond to the output of a model with a strange attractor. Furthermore, following the investigation done by [Faranda et al., 2020], we will explore how the main properties of the N dimensional phase space can be reduced to two characteristic parameters, local dimension d and local extremal index θ . For bivariate

data, i.e. when analyzing time series of two different atmospheric observables, another metric will be introduced to describe how dependent two variables are, the co-recurrence ratio. Other metrics will also be explored later in this study.

1.2 About dimension

Different techniques have been investigated to find the fractal dimension of a set. We are interested in the local, or instantaneous dimension (local in phase space is equivalent to instantaneous), and for intuitive purpose we start by describing the box counting method.

Box counting method consists in setting the length, l , of the sides of a box, and see the number of boxes of N -dimensional volume, $N(l)$, of side l needed to cover the whole set, as $l \rightarrow 0$, where l scales linearly. The number of boxes needed will go with the inverse of l in case the set is a line. In 2D it will go proportional to $(\frac{1}{l})^2$, and in general we have $N(l) \propto (\frac{1}{l})^d$, where d is the dimension of the set, fractal or integer. This gives:

$$d = \lim_{l \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log(N(l))}{-\log(l)}$$

In the case of a discrete trajectory of some attractor in N dimensional space, we are interested in the local dynamics and would like to know the local, or equivalently instantaneous, fractal dimension, d , at some instant in time, t_i . One could then, in a similar approach as for box counting, find the instantaneous dimension at a point ξ of the trajectory, by determining a radius r of euclidean distance to that point, and counting as $r \rightarrow 0$, the number $m(r)$ of points whose linear distance to point ξ is less than r . As $m(r) \propto r^d$, the estimated instantaneous dimension at point ξ would be

$$d_\xi = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log(m(r))}{\log(r)}$$

A more detailed description of the main definitions of fractal dimensions is provided in Appendix A. The box-counting method, and variants thereof, work and have been used extensively, but they are subject to large uncertainty and are computationally expensive.

The technique we will use instead is based on the same idea, but is supported by statistical results of Extreme Value Laws (EVL) [Freitas et al., 2012].

In [Freitas et al., 2009], the use of EVL and Hitting Time statistics allow us to monitor the Poincaré recurrences with logarithmic returns

$$g_\xi(\vec{x}_i) = -\log(\text{dist}(\vec{x}_i, \xi)) \tag{1.1}$$

where $\text{dist}(\vec{x}_i, \xi)$ is the euclidean distance between points ξ and \vec{x}_i , and $\log(\cdot)$ is the natural logarithm.

By taking only the logarithmic returns over a certain quantile, q , we are selecting points inside a ball B centered at ξ , with radius $R = \exp(-\mu)$, where $\mu(q)$ is a threshold determined by the quantile. We call these points the exceedances, and the total number of exceedances is a random variable that follows a binomial distribution $\text{Bin}(n, (1 - q))$, in which n is the total number of points. The condition of having q as a function of n such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n(1 - q(n)) = \Theta$, for some constant Θ (note that Θ is the

1. INTRODUCTION: NOTATION AND DEFINITIONS

expected number of exceedances), makes the binomial distribution converge to a Poisson process with intensity Θ . This condition is necessary to describe the occurrence of exceedances as a Poisson process [Moloney et al., 2019] and thus to follow the generalized Pareto distribution with shape $\Xi = 0$ (which corresponds to the exponential distribution) [Lucarini et al., 2011] 1.2 with density:

$$f_{\xi}(\vec{x}_i) = \frac{1}{\sigma_{\xi}} \exp\left(-\frac{g_{\xi}(\vec{x}_i) - \mu_{\xi}}{\sigma_{\xi}}\right) \quad (1.2)$$

with $g_{\xi}(\vec{x}_i) > \mu_{\xi}$ and $\sigma_{\xi} = \langle g_{\xi}(\vec{x}_i) - \mu_{\xi} \rangle$ by construction. We will refer to points $\vec{x}_i : g_{\xi}(\vec{x}_i) - \mu_{\xi} > 0$, as the exceedances.

Using these previous works, we implement the following algorithm to compute d :

- choose a certain quantile, q , of a sample of n logarithmic returns, to be the threshold over which points are accepted. These points are the exceedances. The bigger the amount of elements in the sample, the higher we must set the quantile q
- get the values for which $g_{\xi}(\vec{x}_i) > \mu_{\xi}$, where μ_{ξ} is the threshold calculated for the point ξ at which we want to compute the local metrics
- the distribution of the independent proportion of the exceedances, θ (see next section), will have the exponential distribution form (1.2), with $\frac{1}{\sigma_{\xi}} = d_{\xi}$, where σ_{ξ} represents the average of the exceedances:
 $\sigma_{\xi} = \langle g_{\xi}(\vec{x}) - \mu_{\xi} \rangle$ (average over time or ensemble average are equivalent due to ergodicity)

To get the total dimension of the attractor, we then only need to take the average of the instantaneous dimensions: $D = \langle d_i \rangle$.

For a more intuitive approach and to relate this methodology to the box counting method described above, let us take a closer look to what is happening. For the sake of simplicity we will remove the subscript ξ , but we assume we are at some arbitrary point ξ :

$$\exp\left(-\frac{g(\vec{x}) - \mu}{\sigma}\right) = \exp\left(-\frac{-\log(r) - (-\log(r_{max}))}{\sigma}\right) = \exp\left(\frac{1}{\sigma} \log\left(\frac{r}{r_{max}}\right)\right) = \left(\frac{r}{r_{max}}\right)^{1/\sigma} \quad (1.3)$$

where r is the euclidean distance, for each exceedance, to the point ξ and r_{max} is equivalent to the radius of the N dimensional ball B centered at ξ . If we set $r' = \frac{r}{r_{max}}$ we have $0 < r' < 1$.

Consider a 1 dimensional sample with r' uniformly distributed (radial density function $f(r') = 1$). By (1.3), we have that $g(\vec{x}) - \mu = -\log(r')$, so by construction $\sigma = \langle -\log(r') \rangle$. This average gives, in the continuous limit:

$$\sigma = -\int_0^1 \log(r') f(r') dr' = 1$$

which is consistent with the definition that $d = 1/\sigma$.

Now consider our sample is uniformly distributed in a 2 dimensional space, we first need to find the radial density function $f(r')$:

$$\mathcal{C} \int_0^1 2\pi r' dr' = \mathcal{C} \pi$$

where \mathcal{C} is a normalization constant, $\mathcal{C} = \frac{1}{\pi}$, so $f(r') = 2r'$.

σ becomes:

$$\sigma = - \int_0^1 \log(r') f(r') dr' = -2 \int_0^1 \log(r') r' dr' = -2 \cdot -\frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{2}$$

and $\frac{1}{\sigma} = 2$ is again consistent with the dimension in which we distributed the points in the first place. We could repeat the same reasoning for dimension 3 and get $\sigma = \frac{1}{3}$, and the same remains valid for non-integer dimensions.

It becomes even more obvious if we make a change of variable to absorb the distribution function in the new variable (like for inverse transform sampling). For example in 2D, changing to a variable x would give $f(r') = \frac{dx}{dr'} = 2r' \rightarrow dx = 2r' dr' \rightarrow x = r'^2$, and σ becomes:

$$\sigma = - \int_0^1 \log(x^{1/2}) dx = 1/2$$

In 3D we would have $dx = 3r'^2 dr' \rightarrow x = r'^3$:

$$\sigma = - \int_0^1 \log(x^{1/3}) dx = 1/3$$

This approach allows fractional dimension to emerge naturally as the inverse of the average of $g(\vec{x}) - \mu$, which is by definition σ , and which is by construction the exponent of the variable r' that scales linearly, analogous to l in the box counting method.

So the method returns the fractal dimension as a function of the radial distribution. In the example above, it returns the exponent of the new variable x by averaging the exceedances $-\log(r')$. This exponent σ makes the correspondence between the linear scaling of r' and the uniformly distributed variable x : $x = r'^{1/\sigma}$, from which we conclude that $d = \frac{1}{\sigma}$ is the fractal dimension. When the distribution of points around ξ is not sufficiently well distributed the method fails in making the correspondence between linearity and uniformity, and may give dimensions which are not consistent with observations, like attributing dimension 6 to a point on a Lorenz attractor, which lies in a 3D space.

Let us illustrate with an example (Figure 1.2). We can create a uniform distribution of 1000 points on a disk of radius 1, as if they were part of a bigger set, consider this disk to correspond to ball B of points over the threshold μ , and take the local dimension of the central point $\xi = (0, 0)$.

Applying the algorithm with $q = 0$ (meaning that we consider all points to be in ball B) we get $d = 2.0774$, corresponding to the 2D space in which we uniformly distributed the points. Redistributing the points from the disk to a 3D sphere with uniform angular distribution, but maintaining radial coordinates gives the exact same local dimension, as we would expect. Despite the fact that the points are now in 3D we still get dimension 2, reflecting the fact that they are not uniformly distributed in the 3D space (they are denser closer to the center).

Taking the problem in reverse, we can simulate a uniform spherical distribution in a 3D space, with (R, θ, ϕ) spherical coordinates:

$$\theta = 2\pi \cdot \text{rand}() \quad \phi = \text{acos}(1 - 2 \cdot \text{rand}()) \quad R = \text{rand}()^{1/3}$$

1. INTRODUCTION: NOTATION AND DEFINITIONS

Figure 1.2: On the left, uniform distribution of points on a disk, and local dimension taken at its center, with $q = 0$. On the right, same radial coordinates as on the left but with isotropic distribution, and local dimension taken at its center. d is equal for both and is close to 2, corresponding to the dimension where the radial distribution is uniform (in this case, the disk).

where $rand()$ is a pseudo-random generator of real numbers between 0 and 1. The algorithm provides us with a local dimension of 3.0397 (see Figure 1.3), and plotting the same radial distribution on an isotropic disk gives a lower density at the center. If the distribution is not uniform the center of the ball is privileged and there is no translational invariance, which does not characterize a proper space. The algorithm returns the dimension that will correspond to a space where points are uniformly distributed.

Figure 1.3: On the left, uniformly distributed points in a 3D-sphere. On the right, same radial distribution, with a uniform angular distribution in a 2D space. d is the local dimension of the central point, provided by the algorithm.

1.3 About the extremal index

The extremal index (EI), usually denoted θ , is a way to measure the tendency of exceedances to occur in clusters. In general, it is the inverse of mean cluster size and it reflects dependences between the exceedances.

1.3 About the extremal index

- A low extremal index (θ close to 0) indicates strong clustering of exceedances, meaning that extreme values tend to occur together in clusters, showing persistency and reflecting the proportion of points belonging to the same cluster
- In contrast, a high extremal index (θ close to 1) suggests weaker clustering, indicating in general that exceedances occur independently, but in our case reflecting low persistency

For a trajectory in phase space, a cluster is a segment of the trajectory that is contained inside ball B centered at ξ , defined by a certain quantile of the logarithmic returns (1.1). We will say that a cluster is a recurrence of the orbit in ball B . That is why θ , in phase space, can be interpreted as the inverse of persistence.

The method we use here to compute θ was developed by Stueveges, she says in her paper [Sueveges, 2007]: *"The extremal index plays a double role: it determines both the proportion of zero and nonzero inter-exceedance times and the expected value of the normalized inter-cluster times."* The second role corresponds to the observation that the normalized mean cluster size is θ^{-1} , and the first role to the observation that θ is the ratio of independent exceedances (proportion of nonzero inter-exceedance times), and $1 - \theta$ is the ratio of dependent exceedances (proportion of zero inter-exceedance times).

For a chaotic attractor, the points of the trajectory cover the invariant set without ever repeating themselves, and the averages can be taken from the entire set without introducing bias due to repetitions, dependencies, or whatsoever. Which is why, for a chaotic attractor it mainly is the inverse of mean cluster size, or in other words a measure of "stickiness" at a given point.

As θ is the inverse of the mean cluster size, it is the number of clusters divided by the total number of exceedances, or in this case, the number of recurrences of the orbit over the total number of exceedances:

$$\theta = \frac{\#cluster}{\#exceedances} \quad (1.4)$$

The inverse gives units of exceedances per cluster which is the mean cluster size. In phase space, θ has dimension $[\frac{1}{ime}]$, as each exceedance of the same cluster is separated by the same time interval τ . Figure 1.4 shows the relation between θ obtained by Sueveges method [Sueveges, 2007] and the method by means of equation (1.4), where we only have considered successive exceedances as being part of the same cluster. We have randomly taken 100 points of a trajectory of 10000 points and computed their local θ with both methods, for quantiles $q = 0.85, 0.9, 0.95$. The methods are consistent with each other for a Lorenz attractor integrated with RK4, $\tau = 0.1$ and $T = 1000$, and seem robust to the choice of the quantile.

Statistically, besides from being the reciprocal of the mean cluster size, $1 - \theta$ is the portion of the exceedances that shows strong dependence and comes as by-product, so to speak, of each independent cluster. We could then think that only a portion θ of the exceedances will follow a proper Poisson process, and because we extract dimension from the distribution of exceedances, that we should consider only this portion θ to compute d . But as mentioned earlier, in this scope, the ergodic nature of a strange attractor gives every point its own significance and equal weight for the computation of average values, and θ has the only meaning of inverse mean time of travel of the orbit through ball B , centered at ξ . We

1. INTRODUCTION: NOTATION AND DEFINITIONS

Figure 1.4: The linear fit gives 1.005 for blue ($q = 0.95$), 1.03 for red ($q = 0.9$), and 1.05 for yellow ($q = 0.85$). All for Runge-Kutta integration with $\tau = 0.1$ and $T = 1000$.

will later demonstrate with declustering (taking the maximum, or median, of each cluster, Figure 2.4 in next section 2.1.1) that this is in fact the case.

Chapter 2

Analysis through numerically integrated attractors

In this chapter we explore the methodology by applying it to the Lorenz attractor and the Baker's map. The exploration through these numerical models provides us with more information before applying the method to real world data. We study its robustness and introduce the metric R , the radius of ball B .

2. ANALYSIS THROUGH NUMERICALLY INTEGRATED ATTRACTORS

2.1 Univariate analysis and Lorenz attractor

To illustrate these metrics, dimension and extremal index (EI), we start by analysing the well known Lorenz attractor (equations 2.1), with parameters $\beta = 8/3$; $\sigma = 10$; $\rho = 28$; and initial conditions randomly picked from a point on the attractor: $x_0 = -1.07$; $y_0 = 4.12$; $z_0 = 27.80$. The fractal dimension is known to be 2.06 ± 0.01 .

The Lorenz equations that define the dynamics:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= \sigma(y - x) \\ \dot{y} &= x(\rho - z) - y \\ \dot{z} &= xy - \beta z\end{aligned}\tag{2.1}$$

For a RK4 integration of this system, with $\tau = 0.01$ and $T = 2000$ we have Figure 2.1 with a mean dimension $D = 2.08$ and a mean EI $\theta = 0.17$. Out of the 200001 points, 2414 have local dimension bigger than 3, which is about 1.2% of the data. These come from edge states that produce higher dimensions due to finite size effects and introduce bias into the calculations. We plot only dimensions up to 3 in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: On top, local dimension d , and at the bottom, local extremal index θ

2.1.1 Graphical exploration

To better picture the logarithmic returns we set ourselves at some point ξ of the Lorenz attractor and compute all the distances, $\|\vec{x}_i - \varepsilon\|$, $i = 0, \dots, n$. We then compute the function $g(\vec{x})$ (1.1), so to each timestep i we have a value $g_\xi(\vec{x}_i)$ associated. We define a threshold corresponding to quantile $q = 0.98$, call it $\mu_\xi = \text{quantile}(g_\xi(\vec{x}_i), q)$, and take all the extreme values above that threshold. In this example we have drawn the trajectory with RK4, with $\tau = 0.01$ and $T = 2000$.

Plotting the points and their respective logarithmic return value $g_\xi(\vec{x}_i)$ in colors we obtain graph 2.2, for $\xi = \vec{x}_{127000} = (3.66, 2.06, 24.25)$. This point has local EI, $\theta = 0.15$ and local dimension $d = 1.96$.

2.1 Univariate analysis and Lorenz attractor

The radius R of the ball B is about 2.6. As we will see this radius will depend on the local density of points, the higher the local density, the smaller the radius of B .

Figure 2.2: ball B , with colors corresponding to logarithmic return values of exceedances. Points in yellow correspond to the center where values of $g_\xi(\vec{x})$ are highest.

We then want to visualize the fit to the exponential density function (2.2) (in accordance with (1.2)). We define $\eta_\xi(\vec{x}_i) = g_\xi(\vec{x}_i) - \mu_\xi$, such that $\eta_\xi \in]0, \infty[$, and from which we define the probability density function, for some point ξ :

$$f(\eta) = \frac{1}{\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{\eta}{\sigma}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

where the subscripts ξ are implied.

Figure 2.3 shows a normalized histogram of the number of points with some value of η , compared with the function (1.2). The exponential pdf fits nicely, meaning that the method is consistent. If the exponential and the distribution of $\eta(\vec{x}_i)$ did not match each other, taking the mean of η to extract local dimension wouldn't make sense.

As discussed at the end of section 1.3, one could question the fact that these exceedances occur in clusters, and thus are not independent from each other, so we explore various methods to get a declustered sample, by taking the maximum η from each cluster, by picking a random η from each cluster, or by taking the average value of η from each cluster. Figure 2.4 compares these declustered samples with their respective local dimension and their respective distributions (2.2).

The amount of points in the sample is considerably less after declustering, for \vec{x}_{127000} we go from having 4000 points to 545, that correspond to the number of clusters (we can again verify that $\theta = \langle \text{cluster size} \rangle^{-1} = \frac{4000}{545} \approx 0.14$.) Even smoothing the caused irregularities the clustered sample seems to be a considerably better fit. By computing the average local dimension after declustering with maximum value, we get a lower dimension than what we expect from the Lorenz attractor, i.e. $\langle d_{dec} \rangle = 1.18$. Taking the average of each cluster doesn't make the fit to the exponential distribution. The average dimension after declustering with random picking is $\langle d_{dec} \rangle = 2.42$, which is closer but still relatively far from the expected value for the Lorenz attractor, while the original sample gives $\langle d \rangle = 2.08$.

These results confirm that declustering is not adequate in the scope of chaotic attractors.

2. ANALYSIS THROUGH NUMERICALLY INTEGRATED ATTRACTORS

Figure 2.3: Normalized histogram of $\eta(\vec{x}_i) = g(\vec{x}_i) - \mu$, for $g(\vec{x}_i) - \mu > 0$, compared with probability density function (2.2) in red.

Figure 2.4: Normalized histogram of $\eta(\vec{x}) = g(\vec{x}) - \mu$, for $g(\vec{x}) - \mu > 0$ of clustered and declustered exceedances, compared with probability density function (2.2) in red. On top-right declustering is done by picking a random point out of each cluster; on bottom-left, by taking the maximum value of η from each cluster; on bottom-right by taking the average value of η from each cluster.

For the sake of exploration, we repeat some of the plots above for three arbitrary points, with $T = 2000$, $\tau = 0.01$ and $q = 0.98$ (Figure 2.5). We then explore the time series of $g_\xi(\vec{x}_i)$, by plotting all the exceedances in the interval of $i \in [2 \cdot 10^4, 2.5 \cdot 10^4]$, and see the agglomeration of exceedances into clusters over time. We verify the intuition built in Figure 1.3 with point 164849 (middle column of Figure 2.5), where dimension suddenly goes to 3.2, due to the distribution being much denser further from the center, resembling more the radial distribution of a 3D attractor.

We find that the edge states of the Lorenz attractor get sparser and sparser as they get closer to the edge. And on the edges, ball B captures a significant part of phase space that is outside the attractor's support. This gives a denser distribution far from the center when represented in a 2 dimensional space with uniform angular distribution, which corresponds to a uniform distribution of higher dimension (see example in Figure 1.3). As a result, edge states of the Lorenz attractor can retrieve dimension higher

2.1 Univariate analysis and Lorenz attractor

Figure 2.5: Each column corresponds to a different point on the attractor. On the top row are depicted the points in ball B , with their respective value of $-\log(\text{dist})$; in the middle row are normalized histograms of the occurrences for each η , compared to the exponential pdf; and at the bottom row are time series of the exceedances that occurred for $i \in [2 \cdot 10^4, 2.5 \cdot 10^4]$.

than 6, and as discussed before in Section 1.2 this is where the method fails to properly describe the local dimension. Appendix A gives a more detailed definition of fractal dimension and its relation with the probability measure (invariant measure in the ergodic limit) on the attractor.

2. ANALYSIS THROUGH NUMERICALLY INTEGRATED ATTRACTORS

2.1.2 An approximation of the rotation around the fixed points through the metrics

Fourier analysis shows a dominant frequency of 1.32 cycles per unit time, for time series of θ , and d . The metrics take significantly different values at every turn when they pass close to the junction of the two wings, so this must be the frequency of the orbit circling around the fixed points. It corresponds to a period of $1/1.32 = 0.76$ and by integrating the equations for that duration of time it can be verified that the orbit in fact goes one time around the fixed point in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: 76 timesteps with $\tau = 0.01$ of the Lorenz attractor (2.1) around fixed point C (2.3) in red. Color bar corresponds to values of θ .

We can look for the eigenvalues of the linearized equations at the fixed points and verify that this frequency is close to what we get from the imaginary part of the eigenvalues.

First we look for the fixed points of the Lorenz equations (2.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} = 0 &\rightarrow y = x \\ \dot{y} = 0 &\rightarrow y = 0 \quad \vee \quad z = \rho - 1 \\ \dot{z} = 0 &\rightarrow x = \pm\sqrt{\beta z} \end{aligned}$$

From which we get 3 fixed points

$$\begin{aligned} A &= (0, 0, 0) \\ B &= (-\sqrt{\beta(\rho-1)}, -\sqrt{\beta(\rho-1)}, \rho-1) \approx (-8.49, -8.49, 27) \\ C &= (\sqrt{\beta(\rho-1)}, \sqrt{\beta(\rho-1)}, \rho-1) \approx (8.49, 8.49, 27) \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

The jacobian of (2.1) is

$$\mathcal{J}(x, y, z) = \begin{pmatrix} -\sigma & \sigma & 0 \\ (\rho - z) & -1 & -x \\ y & x & -\beta \end{pmatrix}$$

And by solving $\det(\mathcal{J}_k - \lambda \mathbb{I}) = 0$, for $k = A, B, C$ we find three eigenvalues with $\mathbf{Re}(\lambda) \neq 0$, so the fixed

points are hyperbolic and Hartman-Grobman's theorem holds.

$$\begin{aligned} A &\rightarrow \lambda_1 \approx -2.67, \quad \lambda_2 \approx -22.83, \quad \lambda_3 \approx 11.83 \\ B &\rightarrow \lambda_1 \approx -13.85, \quad \lambda_{2,3} \approx 0.09 \pm 10.19i \\ C &\rightarrow \lambda_1 \approx -13.85, \quad \lambda_{2,3} \approx 0.09 \pm 10.19i \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.7 illustrates 1000 timesteps of a trajectory on the Lorenz attractor. In red are depicted the three fixed points, and some of the eigenvectors.

Figure 2.7: 1000 timesteps of a trajectory on the Lorenz attractor, integrated with RK4 with $\tau = 0.01$. There are three fixed points, at the origin and at the center of the 'wings'. Arrows show the direction in which the system evolves, and red lines are the eigenvectors of the fixed point at the origin.

We find that fixed points B and C have $\omega = 10.19$, which corresponds to a frequency of $\frac{10.19}{2\pi} = 1.62$ and a period of $\frac{2\pi}{10.19} = 0.62$ units of time. It is a little faster than the 0.76 we got from the Fourier transform, but makes a good approximation.

2.1.3 Robustness of θ and d , introducing R

We are interested in the dependencies there might be between the parameters d , θ , and the radius of the ball B .

The quantile will set a fixed number of exceedances for some dataset, and therefore, at a given point where recurrences of the orbit are denser, the *radius* of ball B will be smaller. We made an hypothetical 2D example in Figure 2.8 where this happens, for recurrences of the orbit with approximately the same velocities (same spacing between consecutive points), and we see that for the left side disk the mean cluster size will be a little less than 4, while the right side disk will have a mean cluster size slightly under 2. This will give two different θ 's and thus following the argument that θ is also the inverse persistency, we will have two different persistencies for recurrences with similar velocities. Inversely a low persistency could mean either fast orbiting or slow orbiting, depending on the distance between each

2. ANALYSIS THROUGH NUMERICALLY INTEGRATED ATTRACTORS

Figure 2.8: Two examples of ball B and their respective logarithmic returns. Both have the same quantile (same number of points in B), very similar velocities, thus supposedly similar persistencies, but have different mean cluster size, thus different θ .

orbit recurrences, which will also be reflected in the size of B .

To avoid misconceptions we will not call θ the inverse persistency throughout this work, and propose an idea of a more precise measure for the speed of the orbit by multiplying θ by the radius R : $\theta \rightarrow R\theta$. $R\theta$ has dimension of velocity [$length/time$], where $length$ is a length of phase space, in the units of the physical quantity being studied. We plot a slice of the time series (for $T = 2000$, $\tau = 0.01$ and $q = 0.98$) of θ and R , as well as their product in Figure 2.9. R and θ seem to have their peaks inversely proportional to each other but with a slightly different phase of about 30 steps of integration.

Figure 2.9: R and θ seem to have their peaks inversely proportional to each others but with a phase difference of about 30 time steps. The dominant frequency of the orbit on the attractor is of 1.32 cycles per unit time, a period of 0.76.

Curious to see their respective behaviors we plot the trajectory in the parameters space (see Figure E.1 in Appendix E). There is no obvious interpretation.

With respect to R we comment that the size of R can be misleading when comparing sets with different dimensions N because it scales with dimensionality, in fact, each coordinate/dimension takes a value of similar magnitude and is added to the euclidean norm, making it grow for every dimension we add.

2.1 Univariate analysis and Lorenz attractor

For R to be a constant distance, coordinates would need to be rescaled when adding or taking away a dimension. Instead, to be independent of dimensionality, we rescale R by dividing by its mean, $R \rightarrow R/\bar{R}$.

Next, we are interested in knowing how T and τ , affect the local parameters θ , d and *radius*. We compute the latter for different lengths of the trajectory by changing the total time of integration, T ; and by changing the steps of integration, τ . We note that the procedure for getting local dynamics of the attractor as a function of T is different than the one as a function of τ . We can increase T without affecting the points already integrated on phase space, it will only be adding more of them, and the point ξ from where we compute the local dynamics of the attractor will not change. But when varying τ , the whole set of points changes. So to be able to compute the local dynamics as a function of τ , we must fix the point ξ on phase space. The way we proceed is to randomly draw the points ξ from the first integration of the trajectory with the first value of τ , and take these points as initial conditions to compute the trajectories of the following values of τ .

Figure 2.10 shows the variation of d , θ and *radius* for 5 randomly selected points of the trajectory, as a function of T , for $q = 0.98$ and $\tau = 0.01$. It seems all of the metrics are stable.

Figure 2.10: On top, local θ at five different randomly selected points, as a function of the length of trajectory T . In the middle, d , and at the bottom, *radius* of the same five points. All with $\tau = 0.01$ and $q = 0.98$.

Apart from the condition that T be large enough to guarantee good statistics (for $T \approx 3000$, in this case), we find a dependence between θ and τ that is easy to explain. τ is the time lag between consecutive points, so it must be inversely proportional to the local persistence. The constant is point dependent, because it depends on the velocity of the phase flow at each point. Here τ affects the density of points (smaller steps lead to higher concentration of points). We see the saturation of θ in Figure 2.11 due to the distance in phase space between consecutive points being much greater than between points of neighboring orbit recurrences, leading to a mean cluster size of 1.

2. ANALYSIS THROUGH NUMERICALLY INTEGRATED ATTRACTORS

Figure 2.11: On top, local θ at five different randomly selected points, as a function of timesteps τ . In the middle, d , and at the bottom, $radius$, of the same five points as a function of τ . θ clearly depends on the timestep, which suggests careful selection of τ for any analysis. All calculations were made with $T = 10000$ and $q = 0.98$.

Next, we explore the dependence of θ , d and the $radius$ with the quantile, Figure 2.12. θ increases abruptly as we get closer to $q = 1$. If we get to a quantile small enough that all orbit recurrences leave only one point in ball B , we will have again that the mean cluster size is 1. The biggest quantile considered (last point on the graphs) is for $q = 0.995$, which corresponds to a subset of $0.005 \cdot 1000001 \approx 5000$ exceedances. This behavior is consistent with its dependence on τ (Figure 2.11), and suggests that θ should be interpreted as a qualitative value rather than a quantitative value, as a relative measure, only meaningful when compared with other points of the system taken under the same τ . It is also important to remember that without considering the radius of ball B , even the relative value of θ can lose its property of inverse persistence. d has a different behavior. It seems more robust and can be regarded as an absolute value.

Figure 2.12: Red corresponds to a point at juncture of the 'wings' of the strange attractor; yellow to a point at the margin of the attractor; blue somewhere in the middle of one of the wings. θ takes an abrupt slope as q gets close to 1, but d has a different behavior. d is a more stable parameter. On the other hand, $radius$ goes to zero, as we would expect. Yellow point shows a slight transition in d around $q = 0.9$, probably related to the distribution of points in ball B on the edges of the attractor, where ball B includes a region of phase space that is not part of the attractor.

2.2 Bivariate systems and Baker's map

Finally it is interesting to see how θ stabilizes if we multiply it by the radius, R , as suggested at the start of this section, Figure 2.13. Yellow point being an edge point with lower density, its radius does not decrease as fast. The radius, with dimension of length, is proportional to the inverse local density, when multiplied by inverse mean cluster size θ which has units $\frac{1}{\#of\ points}$, or dimension $[\frac{1}{time}]$ because for each point we have a time interval τ , the resulting metric is a velocity $[\frac{length}{time}]$. Somehow θ can be combined with different parameters to obtain different quantities: like $R\theta$ represents the local speed of the orbit, and $\theta \cdot (\# of\ exceedances) = \frac{\# of\ exceedances}{\# of\ exceedances\ per\ cluster}$ represents the number of times the system returns to ball B .

Figure 2.13: The quantity $R\theta$ shows less dependence on the quantile.

We conclude from the above the following:

- the choice of τ affects θ linearly, that is $\theta(\xi, \tau) = a(\xi)\tau$ where a is a different constant for each point ξ , proportional to the probability measure carried by the attractor
- the choice of the quantile slightly affects d , but mostly θ when getting closer to 1, making it a relative value, and its interpretation should always be relative to other points
- declustering does not apply to strange attractors under the ergodicity condition
- the method fails in giving the right local dimension of edge states
- we can multiply θ by the *radius*, giving rise to a characteristic length over a characteristic time, that will be a measure of the local speed of the orbit in phase space, and is less dependent on the quantile
- it is important to determine τ and maintain it a fixed parameter for all of the analysis of whatever system we're in. In most cases it will be determined by a natural choice of the concerned data.

2.2 Bivariate systems and Baker's map

To illustrate the procedure that will be followed for a bivariate analysis, we will use the example given by Faranda [Faranda et al., 2020] [Faranda et al., 2017], by computing the metrics of the following area

2. ANALYSIS THROUGH NUMERICALLY INTEGRATED ATTRACTORS

contracting Baker's map, on the unitary square, which has a chaotic attractor (see [Quillen, 2021]):

$$\begin{aligned} x_{i+1} &= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{5}x_i & \text{for } y < 1/3 \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4}x_i & \text{for } y > 1/3 \end{cases} \\ y_{i+1} &= \begin{cases} \text{mod}(5y_i, 1) & \text{for } y < 1/3 \\ \frac{3}{2}(y_i - 1/3) & \text{for } y > 1/3 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 2.14: 10^4 iterations of system (2.4).

The choice of a contracting variant of the Baker's map is necessary because of the loss of precision under iteration of the area preserving Baker's map. 64 bits floating point on Matlab allows a precision of 16 decimal digits, which corresponds to $10^{16} = (2^{3.32})^{16} = 2^{53}$, meaning that by loosing one byte of information per iteration, we loose all information about the initial conditions after 53 iterations. By including the attractor, it becomes possible to loose that information about initial conditions in x , without loosing the global dynamics.

The parameters $d_{x,y}$, co-dimension, and $\theta_{x,y}$, inverse mean cluster size, are obtained with the same procedure as in univariate systems, except now the logarithmic returns to point ξ become:

$$g_{\xi}(\vec{x}_i, \vec{y}_i) = -\log\left(\sqrt{(\vec{x}_i - \vec{x}_{\xi})^2 + (\vec{y}_i - \vec{y}_{\xi})^2}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

where index i is there to remind that \vec{x} and \vec{y} are taken at the same instant in time. We can remove it if we keep that in mind. The rest of computations proceed the same way, using extremes of g_{ξ} over a certain threshold μ_{ξ} , defined by a quantile, q :

 Figure 2.15: 10^4 iterations of (2.4), metrics obtained for $q = 0.9$.

$$\exp\left(-\frac{g_\xi(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) - \mu_\xi(\vec{x}, \vec{y})}{\sigma_\xi}\right) \quad (2.6)$$

where σ_ξ is by definition the mean of the exceedances, which is the reciprocal of co-dimension $d_{x,y}$.

If x and y are independent, $d_{x,y} = d_x + d_y$, otherwise $\min(d_x, d_y) \leq d_{x,y} < d_x + d_y$. Observing local dimensions in Figure 2.15 we can guess that x and y are independent. We observe that at some points, $d_{x,y}$ gets lower than $\min(d_x, d_y)$, reflecting that the method to get local dimension is not exact. Also edge effects must be dominant in this example, by returning dimensions greater than the intrinsic 2D-space.

α is another parameter defined by [Faranda et al., 2020] called the co-recurrence ratio, where recurrence here refers to exceedances, and is defined as

$$\alpha_\xi = \frac{\#\left(\left(g_\xi(y) > \mu_\xi(y)\right) \cap \left(g_\xi(x) > \mu_\xi(x)\right)\right)}{\#\left(g_\xi(x) > \mu_\xi(x)\right)} \quad (2.7)$$

where $\#(\cdot)$ is the number of points under condition (\cdot) . This ratio represents the fraction of exceedances in x that are also exceedances in y , for the same quantile. It is the conditional probability that a point in x be an exceedance, knowing that it is an exceedance in y . It represents the coupling of exceedances.

We would like to comment that for this example normalization was not needed, because we were working on $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ square, but otherwise normalization of the variables would have been needed in order to get valuable comparisons of \vec{x} and \vec{y} . This will be done in all bivariate analysis by dividing by

2. ANALYSIS THROUGH NUMERICALLY INTEGRATED ATTRACTORS

the norm defined as

$$\langle ||\vec{x}|| \rangle = \frac{\tau}{T} \sum_{i=1}^{T/\tau} ||\vec{x}_i|| \quad (2.8)$$

where $||\vec{x}_i||$ is the euclidean norm of point \vec{x}_i , at $t = i\tau$.

Chapter 3

Data based analysis

The data analyzed throughout this work come from ERA5 [Hersbach et al., 2018] reanalysis, the 5th generation of the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) global reanalysis at 12UTC, available from the Copernicus Climate Change Service [Service, 2023]. The dataset is a 151×111 lattice over Portuguese territory, spanning latitudes from 36.42° to 42.59° (about $685km$ from south to north) and longitudes from -10.33° to -5.48° (about $350km$ west to east). Each square of the grid covering an area of about $4.5km$ S-N by $3km$ W-E.

Wind magnitudes are taken at 10 meters and temperatures at 2 meters, while relative humidity is taken at $850hPa$.

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

3.1 Wind and temperature univariate system

Before proceeding with the data driven analysis, we must consider a few major differences, or better say restrictions, to the simulations done using numerical integration.

First thing is that the data at our disposal might be restricted to some timestep, τ , due to physical reasons, data availability, or whatever reason that could possibly limit our choice. We could always increase the timestep τ by grouping the data in subsets but that would reduce the amount of information we have because we wouldn't be able to compensate increasing the total time T , as could be done in the analytical case of the Lorenz attractor. What we can do is choose carefully the quantile, q . Although we find some robustness with regard to the quantile, the latter should be selected depending on the amount of data in the sample. We demonstrate such procedure of fine tuning in Section 3.1.1.

Secondly, the trajectory from the Lorenz attractor is a well behaved function. That won't necessarily be the case with data from the real world, often noisy and in thousands of dimensions. So things like linear dependence between θ and τ will most probably not occur. Another interesting aspect is the declustering on real data, described in Section 3.1.2. We find that the question whether the data should be declustered or not is not as obvious to answer as it was for the Lorenz attractor, suggesting the presence of both chaos and order in our system.

Thirdly, depending on how data was processed, we can get significantly different results, as we will see in Section 3.1.1.

3.1.1 Fine tuning the quantile

We first took 10 years of wind magnitudes from January 2014 to December 2023. We use this example to illustrate how to fine-tune q , and as an example of how data processing can affect the result.

We computed the local dynamics for $q = 0.98$, results are shown in Figure 3.1. Note there is a change happening in the time series of the metrics from year 2020 on (around day 2550).

3.1 Wind and temperature univariate system

Figure 3.1: Metrics computed with the 98th quantile for 10 years of wind magnitudes, from 01/2014 to 12/2023. We observe some discretization of θ and a significant change in the last 3 years, from 2020 to 2023. The data from 2020 on, accidentally came from a different dataset that hasn't been through re-analysis.

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

Figure 3.2: Distribution of exceedances compared to the exponential pdf, for $q = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9$. Best fit should sit between 0.8 and 0.9.

The data from that year on was processed differently, which ended up being reflected in the metrics time series. This unforeseen result shows that the method is sensible to data processing, which was easily identifiable in the time series.

We see that values of θ are discretized, it means that orbit recurrences are closer together than the consecutive exceedances. The majority of exceedances caught in ball B belong to different orbit recurrences, and every time a second point is caught for one of them, a jump occurs in θ . This clearly indicates that quantile 0.98 is too big for the considered data which contains around 3650 points, meaning $3650 \cdot 0.02 = 73$ exceedances. When one of the orbit recurrences acquires 2 points in ball B , θ jumps from 1 to $72/73 = 0.986$. We see some small variations around these discrete values which are due to the more sophisticated method of Sueveges that we adopted.

Knowing that dimension is extracted assuming (1.2), we need the exceedances to fit the exponential function for coherence of the method. We compare graphically the distribution of exceedances with the exponential pdf, as a rule of thumb, for a random point in Figure 3.2. As we increase q we have less points meaning more irregularities, but as q decreases, we grow apart from the extreme value regime. From the graphs we find that the ideal value for q should sit between 0.8 and 0.9. Repeating graphical analysis for $0.8 < q < 0.9$ we find that $q = 0.85$ should make a good choice, we are not too worried about making this choice without statistical tests because the method shows some robustness relative to the quantile. The same procedure should be repeated with a few other randomly picked points, because some points behave better than others. We now repeat the computation of the metrics with $q = 0.85$ and get Figure 3.3. This example illustrates the importance of fine-tuning the quantile to make sure the

analysis is well grounded.

Figure 3.3: 10 years of wind magnitudes, from january 2014 to december 2023. θ versus d . $q = 0.85$.

3.1.2 Declustering on real data

Unsatisfied with the 10 years time series, we repeat the analysis with wind magnitudes and temperatures over the same geographical region with same resolution, for a period of 42 years: 01/1979 – 12/2020. This time fine tuning of the quantile took us to $q = 0.96$. We are now dealing with real data, and the assumptions that the observables display chaotic behavior can be an over simplified assumption. Scientists continue to investigate the multistability versus monostability nature of weather, and its dual nature of chaos and order [Shen, 2022]. For this reason we are interested in checking the effect of declustering on the distribution of exceedances of real temperature and wind data.

We randomly pick point $i = 380$ and display the distribution of exceedances with the different methods, Figure 3.4. The number of bins is adapted to the number of clusters, the 613 exceedances of temperatures are clustered in about 200 clusters, while exceedances of wind are clustered in about 500 clusters. We find a very nice fit for temperature with the random method, but the method shows inconsistency and a second computation gave a dimension of 5.03 (not shown here) instead of the 5.49 displayed in Figure 3.4. We see that the declustering methods give results which are not as bad as for the Lorenz attractor in Figure 2.4. This suggests that in fact the real data contains some non-chaotic features. Eventually the random method with some improvements in its algorithm would be interesting to investigate, but this version is not consistent enough. We content ourselves with the computations without declustering, and we gain some intuition to the fact that the weather observables seem to contain some degree of order.

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

Figure 3.4: Declustering effect on real data, wind magnitude on the upper half, and temperature on the lower half, both for point $i = 380$.

3.1.3 Anomalies and their relations

Figure 3.5: Metrics for 42 years of temperatures, from january 1979 to december 2020, for $q = 0.96$. Only first 10 years of time series were plotted for better visibility. We see seasonality playing an important role in the periodicity of the time series, maximas of d corresponding to winter. θ has two cycles per year.

Figure 3.5 shows the first 10 years of the time series of d and θ , as well as the plot of θ vs d . Resulting plots for wind magnitudes are in Appendix E, Figure E.2.

To be less affected by seasonality we are interested in the anomalies, which consist in computing the difference between the value of a specific day with its average over the 42 years, $\Delta x_i = x_i - \overline{x_{i+n365}}$, where $i \in \mathbb{N} : 0 < i \leq \frac{T}{\tau}$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z} : 0 < i + n365 \leq \frac{T}{\tau}$. This removes a periodic component of the variation at each point due to the yearly cycle of seasons. To get a smoother and clearer time series, we compute the

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

anomalies by averaging x_i with its nearest neighbors x_{i-1} and x_{i+1} .

$$\Delta x_i = \frac{x_{i-1} + x_i + x_{i+1}}{3} - \frac{1}{42} \sum_n \frac{x_{i-1+n365} + x_{i+n365} + x_{i+1+n365}}{3} \quad (3.1)$$

for $i \in \mathbb{N} : 0 < i \leq \frac{T}{\tau}$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z} : 0 < i+n365 \leq \frac{T}{\tau}$. In this case $\frac{T}{\tau} = 15341$, and we take periodic conditions for the limits: $x_{i+1} = x_1$ for $i = 15431$ and $x_{i-1} = x_{15431}$ for $i = 1$. And then we are also interested in computing the average of the square of these anomalies, which is the variance for each day of the year.

$$\text{VAR}(x_d) = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=0}^{41} \Delta x_{d+n365}^2 \quad (3.2)$$

for $d \in \mathbb{N} : 0 < d \leq 365$.

Both are plotted in Figure 3.6 for temperature: Δx_i is plotted after normalization to 0 mean (the mean of Δx_i defined by (3.1) is not zero due to the smoothing) and standard deviation 1, and 3.2 is plotted as relative standard deviation:

$$\sigma_d^{rel} = \sqrt{\text{VAR}(x_d) / \bar{x}} \quad (3.3)$$

We observe an apparently strong relation between the anomalies of temperature and the anomalies of its metrics during the coldest season of the year, with negatively related anomalies during the warmest season. We see also that θ clearly has two cycles per year with higher σ_{rel} in winter and summer seasons, while σ_{rel} of d has only one dominant cycle per year, with its peak in winter. Anomalies of T are higher in spring with a second smaller peak between summer and autumn.

3.1 Wind and temperature univariate system

Figure 3.6: On top: years 1979, 1995, 2010 of anomalies of temperatures (3.1). At the bottom: relative standard deviation (3.3).

To better visualize the positive and negative relations between the anomalies, we turn every positive anomalies into 1 and every negative anomalies into -1 , and sum their products for equal times over each semester of the 42 years. Positive results indicate sign concordance while negative results indicate opposite signs concordance, and the maximum value possible is equal to the number of days per semester.

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

The result is plotted in Figure 3.7. By dividing the result by the duration of the semester, we a sign concordance coefficient.

Figure 3.7: Sign concordance of anomalies of temperatures with anomalies of d (on top), and with anomalies of θ (at the bottom).

The result is very interesting because it shows evidence of the relation between the anomalies of the metrics and the anomalies of temperature. For the semesters chosen (1st of April to 1st of October) the strongest signal is the negative sign concordance between ΔT and Δd that oscillates around -100 , meaning that on around 100 days of the semester ΔT has the opposite sign of Δd , and in the remaining $180 - 100 = 80$ days, half have the same sign and half have opposite sign, giving a total of $100 + \frac{180-100}{2} = 140$ days with anomalies of opposite signs, which is about 78% of that semester.

To optimize this result we allow the start of the semester to vary and take the average of the sign concordance over the 42 years, see Figure 3.8. We find that for 6 months season from 15th of March to 14th of September the sign concordance with both metrics is maximized. The resulting plot is very similar to 3.7, and only slightly better (Figure E.3 in Extra Plots). Interested in the duration of each season we let both the start and duration of each semester to vary freely, in order to maximize the function:

$f(sem1, sem2) = -(anticorrelation_sem1) + (correlation_sem2)$. The interval found to include all possible maximas goes from 01/02 to 30/06 for season 1, and from 01/08 to 30/12 for season 2. The result consistently gives a longer season 1 than 2, and is more balanced than what we had in Figure 3.7 in the sense that positive coefficients become as relevant as negative ones (Figure 3.9). We conclude from the data that opposite sign concordance are more frequent because they extend the first season up to 300 days in some cases, these corresponding to the warm season. Overall, the cold season is reduced to around 4 months while the warm season is extended to 8 months, both sign concordance with Δd and $\Delta \theta$ agreeing.

3.1 Wind and temperature univariate system

Figure 3.8: Mean sign concordance as a function of the start of semester 1. Semester 2 starts 6 months later.

Repeating this analysis to wind magnitudes instead of temperature, we find the results are not as neat (see in Extra Plots, Figures E.4 and E.5). We see that the relation of anomalies of (W, d_W) are consistently negative and out of phase with respect to the ones of (W, θ_W) . Sign concordance of anomalies of (W, θ_W) shows a more comparable behavior to what we had with temperatures, except that we find no clear pattern for the duration of seasons, bringing us to the conclusion that there is no advantage in dividing wind magnitudes in seasons. Exploring the possibility of having more meaningful anomalies by computing anomalies of $R\theta_W$, we compare both anomalies of θ_W and $R\theta_W$ with anomalies of wind (by means of (3.1)), after normalization to 0 mean and standard deviation 1, in Figure 3.10. We find a very strong relation almost all year long with a small tendency for opposite signs concordance in summer, which also happened with (T, θ_T) . The sign concordance is quite strong and can be seen also on the relative standard deviations when brought to the same scale (see Figure 3.11).

Figure 3.10: For the wind, we find that sign concordance of anomalies of $(W, R\theta)$ are much stronger than (W, θ) .

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

Figure 3.9: Duration of each season and respective sign concordance score, maximized for each year. Anomalies of d and T on top, and θ and T at the bottom.

3.1 Wind and temperature univariate system

$R\theta_W$ is a measure of how much the wind magnitude varies from one day to another, because R is the euclidean norm of the radius of ball B where each dimension corresponds to a measure of wind magnitude, in meters per second, and θ corresponds to the inverse of the mean time each orbit recurrence take to travel through ball B , in units of τ (days in this case). The dimension of $R\theta_W$ must then be of $[ms^{-1}day^{-1}]$ and note that it indicates rate of change in absolute value because $R\theta$ is always positive. $R\theta$ stands for daily variability while dimensionality is a measure of variability by means of the characteristic dimension to which the dynamics are restricted. In phase space, d is the range of possible paths, while $R\theta$ is the speed with which this path is taken. What we see in Figure 3.10 are the anomalies, normalized to 0 mean and standard deviation 1. We conclude from the figure that wind magnitudes stronger than average are associated to higher daily variability of wind magnitude, and wind magnitude smaller than average are associated to less daily change than usual. It is as if wind would come in waves, the bigger the intensity the bigger the gap between ups and downs. This could reflect a wave-like pattern of the wind magnitudes.

Figure 3.11: Variance of wind, d_{wind} and $R\theta_{wind}$ anomalies, scaled to standard deviation 1. The relation between wind and $R\theta$ is still visible in variance.

To check that the sign concordances are due to significant anomalies and not to the smallest fluctuations, we plot the sign concordance at equal times (per year for the wind magnitude and per season for temperature), with and without threshold μ , meaning that anomalies Δ , for which $|\Delta| < \mu$ are replaced by zeros. We normalize, for each year (or each season), dividing by the number of days where the anomalies of both series are simultaneously greater than μ in absolute value. This way the maximum value possible if all signs agree is 1. The result in Figure 3.12 for $\mu = \sigma/2 = 0.5$, where σ is the standard deviation, shows that the sign concordance almost double by applying the threshold, which is a clear sign that they are not due to the smallest fluctuations. With $\mu = 0.5$ the mean sign concordance coefficient per year of (W, d) increases from -0.27 to -0.52 , and of $(W, R\theta)$ from 0.50 to 0.90 (see Figure E.6 in Extra Plots). Each day corresponding to either 1 or -1 , we would have zero if the anomalies with same signs would equal the anomalies with opposite signs. This way a coefficient of 0.5 means that $50\% + 50\%/2 = 75\%$ of the anomalies of $(W, R\theta)$ have the same sign without threshold, and with threshold, $90\% + 10\%/2 = 95\%$. For the anomalies of (W, d) we have, without threshold, 63% of them with opposite signs, and with threshold, 74.5% .

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

Figure 3.12: On top, sign concordance, per season, without threshold, and at the bottom with threshold of $\sigma/2 = 0.5$.

The threshold to the temperature anomalies is applied the same way with a season 1 of 8 months, from 15/03 – 14/11, and a season 2 of 4 months, from 15/11 – 14/03 (Figure 3.12). Again, the application of threshold increases the value of the sign concordance, with a mean of (T, d) going from -0.26 to -0.54 and 0.30 to 0.52 , for season 1 and season 2 respectively, and for (T, θ) going from -0.51 to -0.87 and 0.43 to 0.76 , for seasons 1 and 2. By applying the threshold to the series all coefficients are amplified, with a few exceptions of anomalies of d that move in opposite direction, like for example in 1988 and 1989. The mean of the coefficients practically doubles with the use of threshold.

At last we study the variability of the metrics along the years and the patterns of the extreme anomalies in Appendix C. The results show a trend in temperature due to global warming, and a change in the variations of R can be found around year 2002.

3.2 Wind and temperature bivariate data analysis

In summary, here's what we conclude from the anomalies analysis:

- temperature appears to have 2 seasons, with a warm season of around 8 months characterized by a strong negatively related anomalies of temperature with both anomalies of d and θ , and a cold season of around 4 months characterized by the positive sign concordance of temperature anomalies with both anomalies d and θ
- wind magnitude is not divided in seasons, and has a relatively mild negative sign concordance between anomalies of wind magnitude and anomalies of d , and a strong and positive one with anomalies of $R\theta$, suggesting a wave-like behavior
- $R\theta$ reflects variability, similar to d with the difference that d is the range of possible paths, in phase space, while $R\theta$ is the speed with which this path is taken
- extreme anomalies of the different metrics tend to be related

3.2 Wind and temperature bivariate data analysis

For the bivariate analysis we compute the metrics using bivariate logarithmic returns (2.5), exponential distribution of exceedances (2.6) and co-recurrence ratio α (2.7) as defined earlier. All these calculations are made after normalizing the distances in phase space, by $\|\vec{x}_i\| \rightarrow \frac{\|\vec{x}_i\|}{\langle \|\vec{x}\| \rangle}$, where $\langle \|\vec{x}\| \rangle$ is computed by taking the mean of $\|\vec{x}_i\|$ as described in (2.8).

3.2.1 Co-recurrence ratio, α

Let us recall the definition of co-recurrence ratio defined earlier, (2.7), in the case of x being the time series of temperature, T , and y being the time series of wind magnitude, W :

$$\alpha_\xi = \frac{\#\left((g_\xi(T) > \mu_\xi(T)) \cap (g_\xi(W) > \mu_\xi(W)) \right)}{\#\left(g_\xi(T) > \mu_\xi(T) \right)}$$

For the bivariate analysis, phase space has $2N$ dimensions, and the exceedances form a ball B_{biv} around point ξ , with the same interpretation as univariate ball B . The ball B_{biv} does not usually coincide with the univariate ball of exceedances of temperatures B_T and the exceedances of winds B_W . On the other hand point ξ , by definition, is the center of all three balls. The ratio of points in B_T that coincide with points in B_W is given by α . Figure 3.13 shows bivariate exceedances in black (614 points), and the exceedances shared by both B_T and B_W are highlighted in red (80 for point 2045, and 36 for point 10153). The horizontal blue line corresponds to the wind's univariate threshold, and the vertical blue line to the temperature's univariate threshold. These red points are not the closest ones to point ξ , which stands at the origin. θ_{co} of point 2045 is 0.755 which corresponds to a mean cluster size of 1.325. Distances between consecutive points should be close to $R\theta_{co}$, which can be verified by comparing with Figure 3.15. And from the same figure we see that distances should be shorter in summer, and point 2045 corresponds to a summer day, while 10153 to an autumn day, which is in agreement with the respective distances. The fact that the distribution is spread far from the center (in our 1+1 dimension model) is related to local dimension, as seen in Figure 1.3, distances of winds are further from point ξ because wind has a higher

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

local dimension than temperature.

Figure 3.13: Distances of exceedances inside ball B for points $\xi = 10153$ (on top) and $\xi = 2045$ (at the bottom) for univariate and bivariate analysis. Distances of temperature correspond to the x-axis, and the ones of wind magnitudes to the y-axis. Red marks highlight the points common to both B_T and B_W . Bivariate exceedances are in black, and the ratio of the red marked points over the total bivariate exceedances is α .

The black points represented in 3.13 are spread in $2N$ -dimensional space around the point ξ , while univariate exceedances lay in N -dimensional space.

3.2.2 Relation of anomalies

By applying the bivariate method to the same temperature and wind magnitude dataset of the previous sections, we obtain Figure 3.14. We find that θ_{co} drops twice a year, in summer and in winter, and that α has peaks in the summer. For local dimension, it is clear that winds and temperature are not independent at all because d_{co} remains very close to the lowest of dimensions, d_T . Actually we are surprised to see that d_{co} gets lower than $\min(d_{temp}, d_{wind})$ a few times. This again reinforces the fact that the algorithm to compute local dimension is not exact and fails under some conditions, like for example on the borders of the attractor as seen earlier in Figure 1.3.

3.2 Wind and temperature bivariate data analysis

Figure 3.14: First 4000 days of the bivariate analysis of winds and temperatures (1979-1990).

After what has been seen in the univariate section, we choose to analyze $R\theta$ instead of θ alone.

We take the mean for each day of the year, together with its respective standard deviation, for α , d_{co} , and $R\theta_{co}$, by averaging with the neighboring days:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{x}_d &= \frac{1}{42} \sum_{n=0}^{n=41} \frac{x_{d+n365-1} + x_{d+n365} + x_{d+n365+1}}{3} \\ \sigma_d &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=0}^{41} \Delta x_{d+n365}^2}\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

for $d \in \mathbb{N} : 0 < d \leq 365$, and where Δx is computed through (3.1).

The resulting plot is in Figure 3.15. We see α with a significant increase of both \bar{x}_d and σ_d in summer, d_{co} with two cycles per year, with drops in the summer and in the transition between autumn and winter, and $R\theta_{co}$ with a strong drop in the summer and higher σ_d in autumn and winter. Note that by taking σ_d and plotting it the way we did, we are assuming that the distribution of anomalies are symmetrical around the average value, but in fact they are not. Negative anomalies of θ , for example, are less frequent but much larger than positive anomalies.

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

Figure 3.15: In blue are the means for each day of the year with their respective standard deviation in black, computed by means of (3.4).

Again we can plot the normalized (0-mean and stdev 1) anomalies of α , d_{co} , and $R\theta_{co}$ to see how they behave. Figure 3.16 suggests that the sign concordance analysis we did in previous section should also work with these metrics.

Figure 3.16: We see anomalies of α , d_{co} and $R\theta_{co}$ for years 1979, 1995 and 2010, computed with (3.1). There seems to be mostly negative sign concordance between α , d_{co} and α , $R\theta_{co}$.

3.2 Wind and temperature bivariate data analysis

To get an idea of how anomalies correlate to each others we get rid of all normalized anomalies Δ for which $|\Delta| \leq \mu$, where μ is considered a threshold of 0.5. In order to filter noise due to small fluctuations we compute for each point of the time series the modified anomalies, Δ' , defined as

$$\Delta'(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{for } -0.5 \leq \Delta(x) \leq 0.5 \\ 1, & \text{for } \Delta(x) > 0.5 \\ -1, & \text{for } \Delta(x) < -0.5 \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

We take the sign concordance of each day of the year using these transformed series by (3.6), over the ensemble of the corresponding 42 points in the time series (Figure 3.17).

$$\langle \Delta'_\gamma \Delta'_\beta \rangle_d = \frac{1}{42} \sum_{n=0}^{41} \Delta'_\gamma(d+n365) \Delta'_\beta(d+n365) \quad (3.6)$$

where γ and β indicate the metrics in study, and $d \in \mathbb{N} : 1 \leq d \leq 365$.

Δ'_α and Δ'_d are anti-correlated all year long, while Δ'_α and $\Delta'_{R\theta}$ go through different phases, with the strongest one being negatively correlated, from May to mid-October, and a secondary drop in the transition from autumn to winter. $\langle \Delta'_{R\theta} \Delta'_d \rangle$ appears to have some symmetry to $\langle \Delta'_\alpha \Delta'_d \rangle$ with respect to the horizontal axis. The sign concordance $\langle \Delta'_\alpha \Delta'_{R\theta} \rangle$ presents an annual cycle, with negative values from around 1st May to 15th October (defined as the warm season) and positive values out of that period (defined as the cold season). The two other coefficients, $\langle \Delta'_\alpha \Delta'_d \rangle$ and $\langle \Delta'_{R\theta} \Delta'_d \rangle$, when considered together, also present contrasting annual cycles during the warm and cold seasons.

Figure 3.17: Annual cycles of daily sign concordance of anomalies of the metrics, for each day of the year (equation (3.6)).

The sign concordance of $(\Delta'_\alpha, \Delta'_d)$ for each year, and of $(\Delta'_\alpha, \Delta'_{R\theta})$ for each season, are both plotted in Figure 3.18.

3. DATA BASED ANALYSIS

Figure 3.18: Sign concordance per year for $(\Delta'_\alpha, \Delta'_d)$ and per season/season, from 01/05 to 15/10, for $(\Delta'_\alpha, \Delta'_{R\theta})$. Negative anomalies dominate the positive ones.

Chapter 4

Compound extremes and bivariate metrics

In this chapter we will be searching for compound extremes in both space and time, where highest temperatures and strongest winds occur both at the same time and at the same place. We first pick the compound extremes locally, defined by a local threshold at each gridpoint, corresponding to a certain quantile of the subsets of each dimension separately (associated to its respective gridpoint), and later globally, defined by one global threshold for all gridpoints, corresponding to a certain quantile of the total set of the N dimensions $\times T/\tau$ measurements, with $0 < i\tau \leq T$. This allows to pick compound extremes relative to each gridpoint in the first case, and compound extremes relative to the entire region in the second case. We analyze the general behaviors and relations of extremes and replicate some of the methods used in [Luca et al., 2020] and [Faranda, 2023].

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

4.1 Warm-dry compound extremes

The purpose of this chapter is to study the reproducibility of the DS analysis of warm-dry compound extremes made over the Mediterranean region in [Luca et al., 2020], but this time over Portuguese territory. We study the consequences of applying the same methods used over the Mediterranean region to a smaller region.

The referenced analysis of warm-dry compound extremes (CEs) is restricted to the season of June-July-August. For each season, anomalies are computed at each grid point relative to the seasonal average. So the analysis is based on some restrictions in both time and space: to some season at some gridpoint. Then, for each grid point, the days where anomalies of both variables are over (under) the 90th (10th) percentile are coined compound extremes, and these days are then compared to the days where the co-metric in study is also over (under) the 90th (10th) percentile.

Figure 4.1: Annual cycles of sign concordance of anomalies of the metrics, for each day of the year (equation (3.6)).

We apply this method to the warm season defined by the sign concordance of the anomalies of the metrics, as in section 3.2.2. Figure 4.1 shows the resulting plot: negative sign concordance of $(\alpha, R\theta_{co})$, of (α, d_{co}) , and the change for $(R\theta_{co}, d_{co})$ from a decreasing to increasing sign concordance, point to a period compatible with the warm season defined in previous chapter, from 01/05 to 15/10 (perhaps the 15/05 would be more accurate because it is when 2 out of the 3 sign concordances go from positive to negative, but maintaining the same warm season as in last chapter is beneficial). We use the values of temperatures and humidity instead of the anomalies relative to the seasonal average - as long as we restrict ourselves to the same grid point and the same period of time, these anomalies only produce a shift of the data and will bring no changes when it comes to selecting data over some quantile. Our analysis is based on daily temperature and relative humidity datasets from the same ERA5 [Hersbach et al., 2018] reanalysis from Copernicus Climate Change Service [Service, 2023]. We limit ourselves to a rectangular area that includes Portuguese territory and some Spanish ground around it (the same area we used until now for temperature and wind analysis). We have 11 919 data points per day over a period of 15 341 days (from year 1979 to 2020) for each variables.

4.1 Warm-dry compound extremes

We start by defining the warm-dry compound extremes as in [Luca et al., 2020]: days and places where temperature is locally over its 90th percentile and humidity is locally under its 10th percentile. Dynamical extremes (DEs) are also extremes of the dynamical metrics over the 90th percentile. The threshold of the dynamical metrics is global, as the metrics are global as well, while the thresholds for the variables are defined locally.

When placing a threshold corresponding to quantile q , we will be referring to the quantile of the subset of the warm season only (corresponding to 7056 days) and not the full period of 15 341. So for instance by defining DEs over the 90th quantile, we are taking the $\text{truncate}(7056/10) = 705$ highest values of the metric in question. The same happens for compound extremes, they correspond to the 705 highest values of temperatures that are as well in the 705 lowest values of relative humidity, at each gridpoint. A compound extreme day (CED) is a day where at least one gridpoint displays a compound extreme (CE). We find 2175 CEDs. The average number of gridpoints with CEs on CEDs is 1928. On each CED, compound extremes tend to cluster in space. By defining a cluster as gridpoints with CEs happening on the same day, and in any of the 9 first neighbors of each others, we can compute the number and size of clusters for each CED. This allows us to keep only significant CEDs by keeping only those with clusters bigger than some threshold. By filtering out CEDs that have all their clusters smaller or equal to 100 gridpoints, we are left with 1584 CEDs. The resulting map of number of compound extremes per gridpoint, on CEDs, is shown in Figure 4.2, together with the map of thresholds of each variables. We see a much higher threshold on humidity (and lower on temperatures) at the coastline due to the ocean's proximity, and there is a clear change from the *Parque Natural do Tejo Internacional* upwards.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Figure 4.2: On top, the threshold at each gridpoint, corresponding to quantile 90th and 10th of the warm seasons of temperature and relative humidity, respectively. At the bottom, the resulting number of compound extremes per gridpoint, out of 705 univariate extremes of low relative humidity and high temperature.

By looking at the normalized distribution of the metrics on CEDs we find that all of them have a significant deviation from the warm seasons distribution, which corresponds to the days of the warm seasons (Figure 4.3). The z-score (Table 4.1) reveals how far the averages of the metrics on CEDs are from the average of the warm seasons (considered to be the population), where μ_0 is the population mean, \bar{x}_{CED} is the sample of CEDs mean, σ is the population standard deviation, and

$$z - score = \frac{\bar{x}_{CED} - \mu_0}{\sigma} \sqrt{\#CED}$$

This deviation is weaker for R_{co} but still significant enough to say that extremes of all four metrics are related to weather extremes.

4.1 Warm-dry compound extremes

Table 4.1: Comparison of the metrics' distributions: the 7056 days against the corresponding ones of the 1584 CEDs.

	μ_0	\bar{x}_{CED}	$\hat{\sigma}$	z-score
α	0.204	0.337	0.113	46.8
θ_{co}	0.658	0.563	0.075	-50.6
R_{co}	0.208	0.217	0.037	9.5
d_{co}	6.354	5.497	1.221	-27.9
$R\theta_{co}$	0.136	0.120	0.024	-25.2

Figure 4.3: Normalized distributions of the metrics on CEDs and warm seasons, estimated using a normal kernel smoother.

According to [Luca et al., 2020], the highest values of α suggest a strong coupling between temperature and relative humidity, which in turn associates with lesser degrees of freedom, and thus a lower d_{co} . A plot of d_{co} versus α (from the warm seasons) shows that this relation is valid for $\alpha > 0.3$, and is a tendency only. On the other hand the fraction of gridpoints with CEs (which is a measure of intensity of CEDs) is never bigger than 0.5 for $\alpha < 0.3$, so this relation between α and d_{co} is valid (but far from

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

exclusive) on the most intense CEDs.

Figure 4.4: On top, α versus d_{co} of 7056 days of warm seasons, at the bottom, proportion of gridpoints with compound extremes, for each day of the warm seasons, ordered with their values of α .

We also argue that lower θ and higher R_{co} are associated to configurations spaced out in phase space, reflecting rarity of neighbor configurations. By combining them we get the characteristic speed for the orbit in phase space. We find a tendency for slower orbiting on CEDs, reflecting some degree of stability which can be related to the stronger coupling between the variables.

To assess what fraction of CEDs is present in each set of $15341/10 = 1534$ days ranked by their co-metric value, we plot (Figure 4.5) the total time series of each co-metric placed in ascending order (blue curve), and identify the CEDs by red circles. We find that around 40% of CEDs are over the 90th percentile of α and under the 10th percentile of θ_{co} . There is a strong cumulation of CEDs towards extreme values of α , θ_{co} and d_{co} , but values of R_{co} remain relatively sparse, which tells us that warm-dry CEs are not particularly rare configurations.

By computing the number of compound extremes (CE) that occur on dynamical extremes (DE) of α , we get the map of compound extremes corresponding to the CEDs with $\alpha > 90th$ percentile ($\alpha > P90$). Figure 4.6 displays this map as well as the map of the remaining CEDs ($\alpha < P90$). The complementarity between the two maps suggests that the coupling, α , between the two variables strongly determines the main regions of CE occurrences. Highest values are related to CE inland while lowest values are related

4.1 Warm-dry compound extremes

Figure 4.5: Values of α , θ_{co} , R_{co} , and d_{co} and fraction of CEDs that fall in each decile of the ranked time series of the warm seasons.

to CE on the coastline. Considering that α represents the coupling between the variables, it is consistent that dryness is strongly associated to heat inland, but not as much on the coastline, where the vicinity of the ocean has a different impact on warm-dry CEs.

Figure 4.6: Geospatial distribution of compound extremes on CEDs with α values smaller and greater than 90th percentile of the warm season days.

The same is repeated with d_{co} in Figure 4.7. There is some similarity between the maps for $\alpha < P90$ and $d_{co} > P10$, and for $\alpha > P90$ and $d_{co} < P10$, which reinforces the tendency for higher coupling to have fewer degrees of freedom.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Figure 4.7: Geospatial distribution of compound extremes on CEDs with d_{co} values smaller and bigger than the 10th percentile of the warm season days.

The interpretation of these results is that extremes of the DS metrics are strongly related to warm-dry CE. We find that most CEDs occur on days of DEs. Figure 4.5 shows that 39% of CEDs occur on highest extremes of α , almost 41% of CEDs occur on lowest extremes of θ_{co} , and around 33% occur on lowest extremes of d_{co} . Note that 41% of CEDs represent $1584 \cdot 0.41 \approx 649$ days, and DEs are 705 days, which means that practically all (about 90%) of the lowest extremes of θ_{co} and highest extremes of α are CEDs. This also suggests that the DS metrics be a good tool in the categorization of CEDs, by helping to identify their different nature and the regions they are related to.

We verify this idea by computing the mean anomalies (relative to the average of each day of the year (4.1)) of temperature and relative humidity, first on CEDs, and then on days of DE ($\alpha > P90$ and $\theta_{co} < P10$).

$$\Delta x_i = x_i - \frac{1}{42} \sum_n x_{i+n365} \quad (4.1)$$

for $i \in \mathbb{N} : 0 < i \leq 15341$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z} : 0 < i+n365 \leq 15341$.

4.1 Warm-dry compound extremes

Figure 4.8: Mean anomalies (4.1) on CEDs, and on days that have $\alpha > P90$ and $\theta_{co} < P10$ (colormap scales are different for each map).

We find strong positive anomalies of temperature and strong negative anomalies of relative humidity (Figure 4.8) on CEDs (1584 days). Computing now the mean anomalies over the days of DE ($\alpha > P90$ and $\theta_{co} < P10$, each corresponding to 705 days), we get similar results which is to expect because around 90% of each of DEs of α and θ_{co} are also CEDs. We have stronger anomalies for $\theta_{co} < P10$ than for $\alpha > P90$, and stronger anomalies for $\alpha > P90$ than for CEDs (colormap scales are not equal). Because most of DEs of α and θ_{co} are also CEDs, we get to the conclusion that they capture some of the most extreme CEDs. We find that 61% of the days with $\theta_{co} < P10$ are also days with $\alpha > P90$. Figure 4.9 shows how days of those DEs are distributed throughout the year. DEs of α are mainly concentrated from June to September, while DEs of θ_{co} also have days in May and October. Despite that, mean anomalies of days with $\theta_{co} < P10$ are stronger than the ones with $\alpha > P90$.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Figure 4.9: Distribution of CEDs and of days with DEs throughout the year.

To see whether these mean anomalies, $\langle \Delta \rangle$, are significant, we check, at each gridpoint, the value of the z-score (relative to the warm season population):

$$\frac{\langle \Delta \rangle_{warm} - \langle \Delta \rangle_X}{S_X}$$

where $X = CED, DE_\theta$ or DE_α , and S_X is the standard deviation of the sample X : $S_X = \sigma_{warm} / \sqrt{n}$ (for CEDs: $n = 1584$, and for DEs: $n = 705$) and σ_{warm} is the standard deviation over the days of warm seasons, which is the population to which the whole analysis was restricted to. By doing so we verified that all mean anomalies (for CEDs and DEs) of both temperature and relative humidity have a z-score with absolute value greater than 3.

4.2 Warm-windy compound extremes

We proceed in this section with the analysis of warm-windy compound extremes (CEs). As we will see, this analysis shows some differences to the one of warm-dry CEs, because warm-windy CEs are much less frequent and temperature and wind magnitude have a dependence which is not as linear as temperature and relative humidity have. This turns the analysis more complex but also reveals some interesting features. We first compute compound extremes defined by a local threshold at each gridpoint (as we did above), and later from a global threshold, and compare the results and discuss the main differences and similarities with the warm-dry analysis. The days where at least one warm-windy CE occurs are compound extreme days (CEDs).

4.2.1 Local approach to warm-windy compound extremes

The warm season regarding temperature-wind system appears to be from 01/05 to 15/10, as defined based on the sign concordance of the anomalies of the metrics, Figure 4.10.

We compute compound extremes as we did for the warm-dry case, by selecting extremes of temperature and wind magnitude over the 90th percentile of the 7056 warm season days. This results in 490 warm-windy CEDs, with an average of 287 gridpoints of CEs per CED. By leaving only CEDs that have

4.2 Warm-windy compound extremes

Figure 4.10: Sign concordance of anomalies of the metrics, for each day of the year.

clusters bigger than 15 gridpoints, we are left with 349 CEDs. Figure 4.11 shows the thresholds and the geographical distribution of CEs at each gridpoint.

Figure 4.11: Geographical distribution of thresholds and warm-windy compound extremes, from a total of 705 univariate extremes of temperature and wind magnitudes per gridpoint.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

The ranked time series of the DS metrics in Figure 4.12 shows that warm-windy CEDs are also characterized by lowest θ_{co} and highest R_{co} (as is the case for warm-dry CEDs), but with respect to α and d_{co} CEDs are spread through the entire spectrum.

Figure 4.12: Ratio of warm-windy compound extremes in each 10th of the warm seasons, with their respective values.

To assess the effect of the dynamics on α we look for CEs, at each gridpoint, on days $\alpha < P10$ and $\alpha > P90$ (Figure 4.13). The highest values of α identify the region over Cádiz with most CEs, but the number of CEs per gridpoint is still very low compared to the number of DEs, with $p(CE|DE) = 20/705 \approx 0.03$ on the strongest regions. CEs with lowest values of α are spread over almost the full territory, with the most intense region with a similar $p(CE|DE) \approx 0.03$.

Figure 4.13: Geospatial distribution of warm-windy compound extremes on CEDs with α values smaller than the 10th percentile and bigger than the 90th percentile of the warm season days.

In most of Portugal, strong winds are usually associated to lower temperatures, with the usual north-west wind which is cooled down by the Atlantic Ocean. Warm-windy CEs are therefore rare events and

4.2 Warm-windy compound extremes

most of them will appear to have a low α (low coupling). CEDs with highest values of α will tend to reveal areas where strong wind can actually couple with high temperatures. This gives very fewer gridpoints with CEs, with the exception of the south-east region. Note that there are a much higher number of CEs in that region, some gridpoints reaching 90 CEs, almost three times the CEs of the second most intense region (east of Porto). This can be reflected in considerably different weather dynamics of the temperature-wind system in the South-East region compared to the rest of the territory. As the metrics are global, these differences can introduce bias in their interpretation and we argue that the analysis will lose some consistency. Also, the South-East region is in Spain, and will be a competing phenomena to the observations in Portugal. Because we will later want to compare the results with the wildfire activity in Portugal, we choose to continue the analysis over Portugal only.

The relevance of selecting regions with globally consistent weather patterns is important as these metrics are global. In general, literature points to the importance of selecting the regions to compute the DS metrics according to the interests of the study [Luca et al., 2020] [de Luca et al., 2020].

For consistency, we choose to continue the analysis strictly over Portuguese territory, reducing further the dimensions to 6057, and to recompute the metrics accordingly. The sign concordance of the anomalies of the DS metrics point to the same period for the warm season: 01/05 - 15/10. The map of thresholds for wind magnitudes and temperatures are presented in Figure 4.14, as well as the number of CE at each gridpoint. Two areas seem to dominate, one in the north, at the east of Porto, and another in the south, in the Algarve. A secondary area also appears in the center of Portugal. We will later see that this area is also of considerable interest. The choice of percentile 90th gives 272 CEDs, and a total of 53464 CEs.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Figure 4.14: Geographical distribution of thresholds and the resulting CEs per gridpoint.

With an average of 196 CE gridpoints per CED, we choose to keep only CEDs with clusters bigger than 10 CE gridpoints. We are left with 188 CEDs from the initial 272.

We see at the bottom of Figure 4.15 that significant events start to emerge for $\alpha < 0.17$, and even bigger events emerge for $\alpha < 0.05$.

4.2 Warm-windy compound extremes

Figure 4.15: Fraction of gridpoints with CE: on top, fractions ordered by increasing value of α , at the bottom, distribution of days with fraction greater than 20% over the years.

By selecting the days with fraction of CE gridpoints bigger than 0.2 we find that they all have $\alpha < 0.04$ (top of Figure 4.15), and that there are considerably more of such events in the last 20 years (8 out of 10). Out of those days, the ones with smallest α are the 2 August 2003 [Trigo et al., 2006], 15 October 2017 [Pinto et al., 2018] and 24 July 1995.

With these 188 CEDs we repeat the plots from last section to see where the sample stands with respect to the warm season days. The fractions of CEDs in each decile of the ranked time series is displayed in Figure 4.16.

Figure 4.16: Values of α , θ_{co} , R_{co} , d_{co} and $R\theta$ and fraction of CEDs that fall in each decile of the ranked time series, restricted to the warm season days.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Analysing the distributions with the z-score we find a strong deviation from the normal distribution of sample means. μ_0 and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the population (the warm season days), \bar{x}_{CED} is the mean of the 188 CEDs, and the z-score is

$$\frac{\bar{x}_{CED} - \mu_0}{\sigma} \sqrt{188}$$

Table 4.2: Comparison of the metrics' distributions: the 7056 days of the warm season against the corresponding ones of the 188 CEDs. μ_0 is the population mean, \bar{x}_{CED} is the sample of CEDs mean, and $\hat{\sigma}$ is the estimated standard deviation.

	μ_0	\bar{x}_{CED}	$\hat{\sigma}$	Z-score
α	0.093	0.070	0.046	-6.906
θ_{co}	0.762	0.690	0.063	-15.637
R_{co}	0.354	0.485	0.062	28.998
d_{co}	6.725	7.106	1.395	3.738

The general results continue to point to the fact that extremes in the weather variables are also extremes in the DS metrics.

Figure 4.17: Probability distribution function of the co-metrics over the warm season days, compared with the one of the 188 local CEDs, estimated using a normal kernel smoother.

Higher $R\theta_{co}$ may also be associated to lower or higher α 's, and having a wider range of values of d_{co} and of $R\theta_{co}$ on CEDs, motivates plotting the latter in the metrics' space $(\alpha, d_{co}, R\theta_{co})$ to assess whether we can split them into two distinct categories. The clustering algorithm k-means is therefore applied

4.2 Warm-windy compound extremes

after duly rescaling all metrics to standard deviation 1 (Figure 4.23). We see that higher α 's, besides having a lower dimension, display slower orbiting. This can be interpreted as resulting from more stable configurations, with less degrees of freedom (low d_{co}) and stronger coupling (high α). The extremes that are more likely to be problematic from an operational forecasting point of view are those with lower α , as they appear to have more degrees of freedom involved and faster changes in weather conditions, which gives them a less predictable character.

Figure 4.18: Splitting of CEDs into 2 categories using k-means: unpredictable class in blue, and predictable class in green.

We will refer to the more predictable category as the predictable CEDs (CED_p), and to the less predictable as the unpredictable CEDs (CED_u). Plotting the number of compound extremes at each gridpoint, on each class of CEDs (Figure 4.19) we see a clear difference in patterns with more compound extremes for the unpredictable class, but spread into larger areas, while the predictable class is mainly located at the east of Porto and in Algarve.

Figure 4.19: Geographical distribution of local CEs on CED_u and CED_p and respective number of occurrences (colorbar). It is worth noting that the colorbar for CED_u goes to 15, while it goes to 20 for CED_p .

4.2.2 Global approach to warm-windy CEs

By considering all data of temperature and wind magnitudes in all space and time we obtain a set of $15341 \text{ days} \times 6057 \text{ gridpoints} = 92920437 \text{ values}$ for each variable. We define the warm-windy global

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

CEs as the pair of values of wind and temperature that are over their respective thresholds at the same time and at the same gridpoint.

Placing a threshold at quantile 92 to each corresponds to $28.83^{\circ}C$ and $21.75km/h$ and gives a subset of 199 CED out of 20284 global CEs (meaning an average of $20284/199 = 102$ gridpoints with compound extremes per CED). These global CEs form clusters over the territory. As we did in previous section, with the intuition of removing CEDs with insignificant compound extremes we keep only days that have clusters bigger than 5 gridpoints, leaving us with 162 CEDs from the original 199.

Figure 4.20: Probability distribution function of the co-metrics over the total period, compared with the one of the 162 CEDs, estimated using a normal kernel smoother.

Relating the CEDs with their corresponding co-metric values, we can compare the metrics' distribution of the 15341 days with the distribution of the 162 CEDs, see Figure 4.20. We see that θ_{co} and R_{co} have a clearly deviated distribution. Computing the z-score of each subset of the co-metrics CEDs to see where they stand in the mean's distribution, we find that α and d_{co} are about 2σ 's apart, while R_{co} and θ_{co} are further than 20σ 's apart from the mean value of the normal means' distribution.

Table 4.3: Comparison of the metrics' distributions: the 15341 days against the corresponding ones of the 162 CEDs. μ_0 is the full 42-year mean, \bar{x}_{CED} is the sample of CEDs mean, and $\hat{\sigma}$ is the estimated standard deviation.

	μ_0	\bar{x}_{CED}	$\hat{\sigma}$	z-score
α	0.079	0.072	0.041	-2.230
θ_{co}	0.788	0.692	0.063	-19.479
R_{co}	0.364	0.487	0.071	22.149
d_{co}	6.860	6.629	1.391	-2.108

To see how the values of each co-metric are ranked, and which ratio of CEDs is present in each 10th

4.2 Warm-windy compound extremes

quantile, we order the total time series in ascending order and identify the CEDs in red, in Figure 4.21. We find that around 50% of the CEDs have θ_{co} values under the 10th quantile, while more than 60% have R_{co} values over the 90th quantile, and finally more than 25% have α values under the 10th quantile.

Figure 4.21: Values of α , θ_{co} , R_{co} , d_{co} and $R\theta$ and fraction of CEDs that fall in each decile of the ranked time series.

We see that CEDs are characterized with high R_{co} and low θ_{co} , but seem divided into two different categories when it comes to α . By definition, high α 's are configurations that are recurrent in phase space, in the neighborhood of ξ , that reflect some degree of coupling between the variables, and we expect, once again, these configurations to have less effective degrees of freedom, and thus a lower d_{co} . Figure 4.22 shows the values of d_{co} for CEDs with $\alpha > 3rd$ quantile and those with $\alpha < 1st$ quantile of the warm season distribution of α . A clear threshold seems to split the CEDs around dimension 7, the average dimension over the warm seasons being $\langle d_{co} \rangle = 6.7$. CED with highest dimension corresponds to the 2nd of August 2003, a memorable day of wildfires in Portugal.

$R\theta_{co}$ represents the characteristic speed of the orbit as it passes near ξ , we also plot its distribution and verify that CEDs are not as concentrated towards extremes as θ_{co} or R_{co} (Figure 4.21).

By repeating the procedure of plotting CEDs in the DS metrics' space and applying k-means after rescaling, we obtain similar results as in previous section, Figure 4.23.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Figure 4.22: Distribution of d_{co} values for CEDs with $\alpha > 3rd$ quartile and those with $\alpha < 1st$ quartile.

Figure 4.23: CEDs in the metrics space, divided in two categories using k-means.

The geographical distribution of CE occurring in each class of CEDs is presented in Figure 4.19. We see that the number of compound extreme gridpoints of the CED_p are located in the south of Portugal and in the center, over a region that corresponds to the Tagus' river valley, while for the CED_u they spread in different regions, with stronger intensity in the south and virtually none in the north.

Figure 4.24: Geographical distribution of global CE on CED_u and CED_p and respective number of occurrences (colorbar). It is worth noting that the colorbar for CED_u goes to 12, while it goes to 20 for CED_p .

Finally, we focus on CEDs with $\alpha < percentile$ 10 (P10) and with $\alpha > percentile$ 90 (P90) (Figure

4.21).

Because days of extremes of α could also happen one or two days earlier/later than CEDs, we check the difference between a day with low or high α and a CED (differences greater than 2 days are ignored). The result is plotted in Figure 4.25. We find that high α 's have a strong tendency to happen one day earlier than the CEDs. On the other hand, small α 's do not display the same behavior as they mostly appear on the same day. This again suggests that days with high α 's are more predictable than days with low α 's.

Figure 4.25: Number of accounted CEDs in the neighborhood of days of extremes of α , as a function of the days difference.

We conclude that there is a general stratification of CEDs into two major categories associated to lowest and highest α 's respectively, and associated CEDs with high α 's to more predictive patterns, while CEDs with low α 's seem to have dynamics of less predictive nature (higher d_{co} and $R\theta_{co}$).

4.2.3 Discussion

From the above approaches to CEs, first with a local definition of extreme (at each gridpoint), and then with a global definition, we observe that global and local approach seem to be consistent with the fact that CEDs can be divided in 2 different categories: one of higher predictability which we attribute to more common and ordered patterns (loosely speaking: predictable CEDs), and another of more chaotic nature (loosely speaking: unpredictable CEDs), that is of particular interest to the study of wildfire events.

Figure 4.26 presents the geographical distribution of the 10 identified clusters of CEs covering more than 20% of grid points over Portugal (Figure 4.15). It is worth noting that all cases occurred after 1995, i.e in the last 26 years of the analyzed period of 42 years. Three of the clusters are characterized by small values of α , the events of 24th of July 1995 and of 2nd of August 2003 with $\alpha = 0.005$ and the event of 15th of October 2017 with $\alpha = 0.002$. This last event was characterized by exceptionally strong southerly winds associated to the passage of hurricane Ophelia that steered a large number of fires that were responsible for the all-time record of 220 thousand hectares in 24 h [Pinto et al., 2018, Ramos et al., 2023]. The events of 2nd and 3rd of August 2003 took place during the 1-15 August extreme heat wave, the first day coinciding with the largest amount of daily burned area of that year [Trigo et al., 2006]. In turn, the event of July 1995 follows the day with the largest burned area of that year. The remaining events, with larger values of α , took place in June, and relate to very hot days, with all but one (13th of June 2003) marking the first day of the fire season of the respective years with recorded burned area.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Figure 4.26: Geographical distribution of clusters of CEs covering more than 20% of gridpoints over Portugal. Maps with clusters for two consecutive days show the distribution for the first (second) day in red (blue).

Finally, we compare the global and local compound extremes distributions throughout the months (from May to October). We find that they have a similar distribution, but have only 84 days in common, which is a little less than half of the local CEDs and about half of the global CEDs.

We find one important but subtle difference: local dimension of CEDs from the local approach seem to accumulate towards higher extremes, while it accumulates towards lowest extremes on the global approach. Because we are interested in the more chaotic nature of these days, perhaps the approach displaying higher local dimension be of greater interest, which is the local approach.

Figure 4.27: Number of CEDs per month, for both the local approach (in blue) and the global approach (in red).

4.3 Modeling through DS metrics

To see if the DS metrics can serve as predictors for the ratio of gridpoints with CEs on a specific day, we use them on a regression least square boosting method (LSBoost on Matlab). Using the function *fitensemble()* with *LearnRate* = 0.1 and *NumLearningCycles* = 150 (parameters that minimized least squared error (LSE)), and 10-fold cross validation, we were able to get some results for both local (temperature locally above 90th quantile and humidity under 10th quantile) and global (temperature globally above 92nd quantile and humidity under 8th quantile) approach on warm-dry CEs on portuguese territory only (warm-windy CEs hadn't enough CEDs to properly train the model with those thresholds: 2775 warm-dry CEDs versus 199 warm-windy CEDs for the global approach, and 1760 warm-dry CEDs versus 490 warm-windy CEDs for the local approach). We do that for a warm season from 1st of May to 15th of October.

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

Figure 4.28: On top, model for warm-dry CEs using local CEs, and at the bottom using the global CEs, both with warm season days only. Local model shows better performance.

Figure 4.28 shows the result of using all 10 metrics (4 bivariate, and 2×3 univariate) on the 7056 warm season days for both the local and global approaches (we restrict the global approach as well, for comparison with the local one). The LSE ($\sum(predicted - observed)^2$) is of 10.11 for the local approach and of 25.18 for the global approach. The global approach contains more CED. Most of the LSE of the global approach seems to come from the lowest ratios - the model seems more accurate on bigger ratios. The local approach seems to be more consistent, with a linear regression with $R^2 = 0.94$.

To see which metrics (univariate or bivariate) have a stronger impact on the model we train it using only the univariate metrics and then the bivariate metrics. The univariate model has a smaller LSE than the bivariate model and we could see considerably better predictions. This result could be only due to the fact that we have more data to train the model using the univariate metrics (which are 6) than the bivariate metrics (which are 4). But using a Minimum Redundancy Maximum Relevance (MRMR) algorithm, we rank the metrics for each approach in Table 4.4. We find that univariate metrics occupy the first three places in the ranking, with α coming in 4th place.

4.3 Modeling through DS metrics

Table 4.4: Ranking of feature importance by MRMR algorithm, on the prediction of local and global CEs.

metric	local rank	global rank
α	4th	4th
θ_{co}	7th	5th
R_{co}	10th	8th
d_{co}	9th	9th
θ_T	1st	7th
R_T	5th	3rd
d_T	6th	2nd
θ_H	3rd	1st
R_H	2nd	10th
d_H	8th	6th

On both approaches, the bivariate metrics R_{co} and d_{co} stand in the least important features.

We've tried to use the same method of LSBoost to get a model that would predict, one day in advance, the ratio of warm-dry CEs, but without success.

To see if we can get some results for the warm-windy CEs, we can decrease the thresholds to the 80th quantiles. This gives a number of CEDs of the same order of magnitude as for warm-dry CEs (2847 on the global approach and 1378 on the local approach). The *LearnRate* was set to 0.2 and *NumLearningCycles* to 100 to minimize LSE. Figure 4.29 shows each of the global and local models, both applied to the days of warm seasons only, for better comparison.

Figure 4.29: On the left, model for warm-windy CEs using local CEs, and on the right using the global CEs, both with warm season days only.

Modeling the ratio of CEs of the temperature-wind system based on the DS metrics appears more challenging than for the temperature-humidity system, in which warm-dry CEs often cover large areas, making them easier to reflect in global metrics. We also argue that warm-windy CEs have a higher degree of nonlinearity. We've separated the days of the warm season according to the predictable and

4. COMPOUND EXTREMES AND BIVARIATE METRICS

unpredictable categories, for a quick evaluation of the LSBoost's performance to model each of these separately, but the results didn't lead to any relevant conclusion.

4.3.1 Trend of α vs temperature

By dividing the entire territory (including the part outside the Portuguese border) in subregions of 10 by 10 lattice units (areas of about $30km \times 45km$) we can compute the series of α for each of these subregions. To get an idea of the effect of global warming on the values of α during the warm seasons, for each subregion, we do a linear regression of seasonally averaged α 's (1st of May to 15th of October of each year, 42 values for each subregion) as a function of seasonally averaged temperatures (at each subregion). We then plot the value of this trend for each subregion on Figure 4.30.

This gives an idea of the changes in wind-temperature coupling as temperature increases due to climate change. The trend is of 1 order of magnitude smaller than the average of all seasonally averaged α 's of all subregions ($\langle \alpha \rangle = 0.05$), and is the variation of α per $^{\circ}C$, so these are changes in the average α of a little less than 10% per $^{\circ}C$ of temperature increased. The trend is positive everywhere, and reflects an increasing coupling between wind and temperature. Some regions show a higher trend than others, and we recognize some of the patterns seen in previous maps of temperatures. The north of Portugal would seemingly suffer a greater increase in coupling between wind and temperature than the south. However, this does not say whether the coupling is with respect to warm-windy, warm-quiet, or mild-mild configurations (it may not be related to extremes).

Figure 4.30: Map of linear regression of averaged α as a function of averaged temperatures (averages over the seasons), over regions of $30km \times 45km$.

4.4 Coarsening the lattice

Computationwise it takes a lot of energy to compute all the distances of the 15 341 days over the 11 919 dimensions (or 6057 when disregarding Spanish ground). If we use the fact that the metrics are global

4.4 Coarsening the lattice

and show little sensitivity to coarsening, we can try to reproduce the analysis with coarsened data, and compare with the original one. This would considerably reduce the computational costs when spatial resolution can be diminished.

By averaging out the 9 closest lattice neighbors at every 3 gridpoints we go from having a lattice of 151×111 to 50×37 . The space resolution goes from lattice squares of about $3 \times 4.5\text{km}$ to $9 \times 13.5\text{km}$, which is still an acceptable resolution. By computing the metrics in that space, we find very similar results, both in space and time, without being able to see any major differences. See Appendix B for detailed comparison of the different scales of the system.

When comparing the coarsened and original α 's of each day, the biggest relative difference found is still relevant $-1.14 < \frac{\alpha - \alpha_{\text{coarse}}}{\alpha} < 1.00$. The distribution of these relative differences is plotted on the right in Figure 4.31, with a standard deviation of 0.05 (5%). We tried to find something that would characterize the days with bigger relative difference in α 's but found only that February 2012 appears several times in these days, and is by far the driest February in those 42 years.

Figure 4.31: Relative differences between the original α and the coarsened α_{coarse} .

The conclusion is that the method is robust to coarsening, with little information loss.

Chapter 5

From extreme events to DS metrics

In this chapter we search for the signature of the co-metrics of the bivariate system related to specific extreme events. The analysis will focus on the weather conditions associated to the risk of wildfires, and other aspects like fuel or topography, that also contribute to wildfire risk are not assessed here.

The 20 days of most intense wildfires (in burned area) during the study period are plotted in Figure 5.1. The days of reference will be those with more than 10000 hectars of burned area, which correspond to 60 days of intense wildfire (DIW) from 1980 to 2020.

Figure 5.1: 20 most intense days in burned area by wildfires, with 15/10/2017 and 02/08/2003 ranking first and second, respectively.

5.1 Metrics signature

We take the DIW and check how far over (under) the thresholds they are (as defined by the 90th (10th) percentile of wind speed and temperature). We often find that the threshold on wind is too high and that there is no event over the threshold, so no CE. But as we will be analyzing the 15th of October 2017 in more detail, we will leave the thresholds as they are, knowing that to involve configurations of less extreme cases of wildfires, the quantile applied to wind speed might have to be considerably lower (in fact we will see in next section that wildfires can be classified into strong and soft wind configurations through the metrics).

By ranking the time series in ascending order (Figure 5.2), and identifying the values corresponding to the 15th of October 2017 and the 2nd of August 2003 (the first and second strongest DIW) we find some of the lowest values of α out of the 15341 days, more precisely the 4th and 15th lowest values, respectively. The values of R_{co} are within the 200 highest values, which is also a significant extreme, and d_{co} of the 2nd of August 2003 is also the 22nd highest value of local dimension.

Figure 5.2: Values of the co-metrics for 15/10/2017 and 02/08/2003, with the corresponding α in 4th and 15th place, respectively. For α only the yellow circle is visible because it covers the red circle, which is on the same spot.

A low α means that the configuration of wind has a very low coupling with the temperature configuration. High R , on the other hand, tells us that these are also rare configurations, not the rarest but still in the top 200 rarest out of 15341. The neighboring values of α for October 2017 are plotted in Figure 5.3.

5. FROM EXTREME EVENTS TO DS METRICS

Figure 5.3: Values of α in October 2017.

The effect that extremes of α have on the other metrics was further explored in Appendix D.

The same analysis as in previous chapter was performed for the 60 days of intense wildfires (DIW). Figure 5.4 presents the obtained plots for both bivariate metrics of temperature and wind, as well as of temperature and humidity. Bivariate temperature-humidity metrics of DIW show a very clear pattern with highest α_{TH} 's, lowest θ_{TH} , highest R_{TH} and lowest d_{TH} . On the other hand, temperature-wind metrics of DIW have α_{TW} and d_{TW} distributed throughout their respective spectrum. As to be expected, the distribution of DIW temperature-wind metrics are very similar to the ones found in the previous section for warm-windy CEs. Because of the large variability of the influence of wind on wildfires, we will later categorize them into those strongly influenced by wind and those less influenced.

Figure 5.4: The 60 DIW with more than 10000 hectares of burned area over Portugal, and their respective bivariate metric values: temperature-wind on the left, temperature-humidity on the right.

As shown in Figure 5.5, when plotting the 60 DIW in parameters space, we find a similar pattern as the one obtained in the last section (high dimension associated to smaller coupling and higher speed in phase space) for the temperature-wind system, but for temperature-humidity system $R\theta_{TH}$ doesn't seem to play the same role (Figure 5.5, right panel). Applying kmeans after scaling the metrics, and highlighting in red the 20 top DIW, we find that they are equally spread between the two clusters of the temperature-wind system while they are more concentrated in the blue cluster, with higher coupling and lower dimension, of the temperature-humidity system.

5. FROM EXTREME EVENTS TO DS METRICS

Figure 5.5: The 60 DIW in parameter space. The 20 top DIW are highlighted in red.

When taking the average wind magnitude, over the entire territory, of each DIW we find that blue cluster DIW have stronger average wind than those of green cluster, with only a few exceptions (left of Figure 5.6). We find that those DIW with lower coupling, higher dimension and higher speed in phase space (corresponding to the unpredictable CEDs of previous section) are associated to stronger winds. On the other hand, DIW with stronger temperature-humidity coupling are those with lowest relative humidity (right of Figure 5.6). This distinction is not as clear as for temperature-wind metrics, except for the 20 top DIW.

Figure 5.6: Average wind magnitude (left panel), and average relative humidity (right panel) for each of the 60 DIW, as stratified into 2 clusters.

For temperature-wind system we find (similar to previous section) that DIW can be classified in two categories that reflect the impact of the wind, DIW with stronger winds having metrics configurations very similar to those of the unpredictable CEDs configurations of previous section (4.19).

5.2 From analogs to metrics

Following the procedure proposed by [Faranda, 2023], we started by extracting 40 bivariate analogs to 15/10/2017 (the 3 days before and after this date having been previously excluded from the dataset). At each gridpoint we computed the average of temperature T and wind speed W for the 40 analogs. We then computed at each gridpoint the differences ΔT and ΔW between the values of T and W for

5.2 From analogs to metrics

15/10/2017 (Figure 5.7, left panel) and the respective mean values of the analogs (Figure 5.7, central panel). A significance test was finally applied to the obtained differences, by computing the standard deviation across a 1000 bootstrap sample means, each derived from a resample of 40 values of T and W . Gridpoint values of ΔT and ΔW (Figure 5.7, right panel) that were lower than the respective standard deviation were considered as statistically non-significant and set to zero.

Figure 5.7: Maps of temperature (top row) and wind speed (bottom row) values for 15/10/2017 (left panels), for 40 analog means (central panel) and for the respective differences (right panel). Green pixels represent statistically non-significant differences.

Obtained maps of ΔT and ΔW show that temperatures of 15/10/2017 were much higher than usual at distances less than 100km from the coastline, and at least a few degrees higher over almost all Portugal. Wind magnitudes, on the other hand, were particularly stronger inside the triangle defined by Porto, Nazaré, and Viseu, and between Viseu, Guarda and Castelo Branco. Southwestern Portugal, from Faro to Lisbon, also displays stronger winds, but weaker winds than usual appear in the north from Vila Real to Bragança. According to [Simões and Pinto, 2018], cyclone Ophelia was located a few hundreds kilometers northwest of Portugal on that day, and strong southerly winds were registered. Turbulences might have occurred due to warm air coming from African continent meeting the cold air of the Atlantic ocean.

All dates of the analogs fall in the warm season defined as the period between 01/05 and 15/10, the only exception falling at the end of April 2020 (see Figure 5.1 and 5.8). The fact that all analogs fall in the warm season is encouraging, suggesting subdividing the year into a cold and a warm season (see section 3.6).

5. FROM EXTREME EVENTS TO DS METRICS

Table 5.1: 40 analogs of 15/10/2017.

1979_08_18	1993_07_18	2003_09_19	2015_08_30
1980_06_03	1994_07_12	2004_09_23	2016_07_21
1983_09_23	1995_10_08	2006_05_27	2016_07_22
1983_09_24	1996_06_06	2006_06_06	2017_07_24
1990_07_05	1997_05_01	2006_08_26	2019_05_07
1990_08_07	1998_06_19	2009_05_28	2020_04_28
1990_09_27	1998_07_13	2010_08_12	2020_07_27
1991_08_08	2000_06_17	2010_08_31	2020_07_29
1992_05_16	2002_07_13	2011_10_01	2020_08_22
1992_09_16	2002_07_30	2015_07_29	2020_09_08

Figure 5.8: Monthly distribution of analogs.

When plotting the metrics signature of the analogs compared with the full period 1979-2020 (Figure 5.9) we find, as expected, a concentration of points at low α 's and high R 's. In turn, θ_{co} accumulates to smaller values, but d_{co} appears to have two clusters. This might mean that we are catching days with two different types of patterns, suggesting that the choice of 40 analogs may be too high. The lower cluster of d_{co} dissolves for a choice of 10 analogs instead of 40.

Figure 5.9: Values of the metrics and fraction of analogs that fall into each decile of the ranked time series.

However, reducing to 10 analogs reduces considerably the statistical significance of the sample and displays less significant differences in ΔT and ΔW , but it is worth studying (Figures 5.10 and 5.11). Note that only one analog is left in August and one in July, leading to the conclusion that the configurations with lower d_{co} were the ones corresponding to the hottest months (July and August), while others are from a transition period between spring-summer, and summer-autumn (June and September). Despite being left without analogs from the hottest months, the temperatures of the 10 averaged analogs are considerably higher than the one from the 40 (Figure 5.7).

Figure 5.10: Map of the 10 analogs of the 15/10/2017 and significant differences.

When using 10 analogs, we still find some significant values of ΔT , but these are considerably smaller than the those computed from the 40 analogs (Figure 5.7). On the other hand, winds still display significant values of ΔW . There seems to be a very anomalous wind configuration on 15/10/2017, most

5. FROM EXTREME EVENTS TO DS METRICS

probably induced by cyclone Ophelia. Results therefore suggest that temperature configurations were not as anomalous as wind configurations on 15/10/2017, and that winds were an important factor to characterize that DIW (in fact, 15/10/2017 belongs to the windy/blue cluster in Figures 5.5 and 5.6).

Figure 5.11: Monthly distribution of the 10 analogs and respective metrics signature.

It is worth emphasizing that we used the co-dimension d_{co} metric to help select the most representative analogs of the 15/10/2017. By choosing 10 instead of 40 analogs we see the temperature pattern was actually not as anomalous as it seemed while wind magnitudes were still significantly different, a result that is in agreement with studies that point out the major role of cyclone Ophelia on the wildfires of 15/10/2017 [Pinto et al., 2018, Ramos et al., 2023, Simões and Pinto, 2018]. In the previous section, the metrics also helped us characterizing the DIW into most and least windy configurations, using the same method of the previous chapter for the division of CEDs into predictable and unpredictable categories. This suggests that wind plays a crucial role in the division of CEDs into days of more predictable, and less predictable, character.

Appendix A

Different definitions of dimension

There are several methods to obtain the fractal dimension of an attractor, and each of them has given rise to slightly different definitions. Here's a wrap up of its main definitions [Falconer, 2003].

Capacity, box-counting, or Minkowski-Bouligand dimension is one of the first and most intuitive definitions of fractal dimension, the first documented use of the box-counting method was in 1918 by mathematician Felix Hausdorff.

Consider an N -dimensional Euclidean space: we take a set V of that space and want to cover it with boxes of side ε , in a grid-like manner. V should be approximately equal to n times ε^d , with d corresponding to the dimension and n is the number of boxes necessary to cover V , $n(\varepsilon) = V/\varepsilon^d$. As we decrease the linear side ε of the boxes by taking the limit $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, we get the box-counting dimension of the set V , d_{box} :

$$\begin{aligned} n(\varepsilon) &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{V}{\varepsilon^d} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\varepsilon^d} \\ &\equiv d_{box} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log(n(\varepsilon))}{\log(1/\varepsilon)} \end{aligned}$$

To get the dimension of an attractor, substitute V by its supporting set and consider the non-empty boxes only. Experimentally, we are often faced with situations where this limit doesn't exist, so other methods have later been developed.

Hausdorff dimension is a successor of the box-counting method. It is a very similar method, and often equivalent, but instead of a grid of boxes of side ε , we consider non-empty subsets U of N -dimensional Euclidean space with diameter $|U|$ at most ε . We cover the set V with those non-empty subsets, i.e. $V \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} U_i$ with $0 \leq |U_i| \leq \varepsilon$, and approach the limit as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$

$$\mathcal{H}^s(V) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\inf \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |U_i|^s : \{U_i\} \text{ is a cover of } V \right\} \right]$$

$\mathcal{H}^s(V)$ is the infimum of the sum of hyper-volumes of the subsets U_i needed to cover V . It is called the Hausdorff measure. When s is smaller than the dimension of V , the number of subsets U_i needed to cover V will go to infinity, i.e. $\mathcal{H}^s(V) \rightarrow \infty$, but when s is greater than the dimension of V , $\mathcal{H}^s(V) \rightarrow 0$. The critical value where $\mathcal{H}^s(V)$ goes from ∞ to 0 is called the Hausdorff dimension:

A. DIFFERENT DEFINITIONS OF DIMENSION

$$d_{Haus} = \inf\{s : \mathcal{H}^s(V) = 0\} = \sup\{s : \mathcal{H}^s(V) = \infty\}$$

We can usually take other classes of coverings and still get the same Hausdorff dimension. Very often, the subsets U_i used to cover V are considered to be spheres of radius ε . The covering elements can overlap each other and are not grid dependent, which makes the covering of V more flexible and can result in a smaller dimension than the box-counting method. The Hausdorff measure makes the Hausdorff dimension mathematically more concise than the box-counting method.

The packing dimension has a similar definition to the Hausdorff dimension but instead of overlapping elements, we require that elements in the covering of V are disjoint. We first define

$$\mathcal{P}_\varepsilon^s(V) = \sup\left\{\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |B_i|^s : \{B_i\} \text{ is a collection of disjoint spheres of radius at most } \varepsilon \text{ and centered in } V\right\}$$

and $\mathcal{P}_0^s(V) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{P}_\varepsilon^s(V)$. If we consider a countable dense set, we find that $\mathcal{P}_0^s(V)$ has no countable additivity, and so is not a measure. This is corrected by considering V as the union of V_i subsets, leading to the following definition of the packing measure:

$$\mathcal{P}^s(V) = \inf\left\{\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{P}_0^s(V_i) : V \subset \bigcup_{i=0}^{\infty} V_i\right\}$$

And now the packing dimension is defined the same way as the Hausdorff dimension:

$$d_{pack} = \inf\{s : \mathcal{P}^s(V) = 0\} = \sup\{s : \mathcal{P}^s(V) = \infty\}$$

Packing dimension is considered to be the dual of Hausdorff dimension. Figure A.1 shows the intuitive difference between packing, Hausdorff and box-counting methods.

In general $d_{pack} \leq d_{Haus} \leq d_{box}$, and for manifolds these three definitions coincide.

Figure A.1: Packing, Hausdorff, and box-counting methods from left to right respectively. Image by Prokofiev - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=12112582>

Information dimension (Entropy or Kolmogorov-Sinai invariant) is obtained from the invariant measure ρ carried by the attractor and is very useful in practical applications. We start by partitioning

the supporting set of the attractor into boxes of size ε , and find Shannon's entropy to be:

$$I(\varepsilon) = - \sum_{i=1}^{N_B} \rho_i(\varepsilon) \log(\rho_i(\varepsilon))$$

where N_B represents the number of boxes, and $\sum_{i=1}^{N_B} \rho_i = 1$. We then want to know how this information scales with ε :

$$d_{info} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{I(\varepsilon)}{\log(1/\varepsilon)} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Equation A.1 is the weighted average of the dimension of each individual box, obtained from their local invariant measure. Note that there are some similarities with the method used in this study to obtain the dimension of the attractor by averaging out local dimensions that also make use of the local distribution of points in phase space, from a trajectory long enough to be approaching the ergodic limit. The difference lies in that the above method is a fixed-size method (all boxes have the same size), based on the scaling of the probability measure with ε , while our method is a fixed-mass method (all balls have the same number of points), based on the scaling of the average distance of points to the center with mass (where mass is the number of points).

Other definitions can be given depending on the scaling behavior to be studied. Correlation dimension, for example, is obtained by counting the pair of points at a distance smaller than ε , through the correlation integral, but the overall thinking is the same as described above, and for smooth distributions on an attractor, at ergodic limit, they should provide very similar results.

Appendix B

Rescaling the lattice and reducing dimensionality

Next thing we do is to rescale the 151×111 lattice by dividing it in squares of 3×3 and replacing each of them by the average of the values they contain. We repeat this several times, and for each rescaling we compute the local metrics, with the intention of comparing them and see how much information is lost.

The first rescaling leaves us with a lattice of 50×37 , the second one with 16×12 and the third one with a 4×3 lattice. We loose some of the right side rows and some of the bottom lines in the process every time the sides of the lattice are not multiples of 3, but will neglect that loss for the time being. Note that we reduce dimensionality of about an order of magnitude every time we rescale. The resulting metric series are plotted for the first 300 days in Figure B.1, and shows that not much changes, suggesting that reducing dimensionality is an option. The same Figure for wind magnitude is plotted in Extra Plots chapter, Figure B.2.

Reducing dimensionality reduces considerably the computation costs at the time of computing the distances between each point in phase space.

Figure B.1: The 4×3 lattice gets off track more often than the others. R is replaced by $R' = R/\bar{R}$ to make it independent of dimensionality. The same Figure for winds can be found in Extra Plots, Figure B.2.

B. RESCALING THE LATTICE AND REDUCING DIMENSIONALITY

Figure B.2: The 4×3 lattice gets off track more often than the others but looks like it still is a good representation of the dynamics. R is replaced by $R' = \frac{R}{R}$.

Figure B.3: Mean over the 42 years of each metric, for each lattice size.

We observe that local dimension suffers most for lattice 4×3 , which seems normal since it reduces

dimensionality to 12, when local dimension of the original 151×111 lattice has a maximum of 13.6. The anomalies nevertheless are still well conserved, as we can see in Figure B.4, with only some loss of intensity for lattice 4×3 and 16×12 .

Figure B.4: Anomalies of d for different lattices of temperature over the same area, for years 1979, 2003 and 2015.

The averages of each metric are taken over the 42 years in Figure B.3. They are very stable with the exception of d_T that falls for lattice 4×3 , and d_W that start falling already with lattice 16×12 . R reduces with dimensionality, but R' is stable and robust, as we can see in Figure B.1. Anomalies of mean temperature and wind magnitude themselves do not present much interest. To do any comparisons we would need to compute them at each lattice point, and make a correspondence to the points of the rescaled lattice.

We plot the sign concordance of anomalies (T, θ) , in Figure B.5, to see how it evolves with rescaling. The resulting relations are barely affected by rescaling.

B. RESCALING THE LATTICE AND REDUCING DIMENSIONALITY

Figure B.5: Sign concordance of anomalies (T, θ) for each lattice size. They are barely affected.

Dimensionality reduction through rescaling of the lattice suggests that all metrics are robust, and that detailed resolution is not needed to obtain the global dynamics of the system. Rescaling is conditioned by local dimension that should not be higher than the dimension to which we reduce the system, but anomalies still seem to survive even if that was to happen. The geographically local dynamics don't seem to be displayed by the metrics in study, as averaging out local temperature differences barely affects them. At least for temperatures, the metrics seem to express global dynamics only, and are only local in time. For wind we see some more deviations from the original lattice, but the core anomalies still remain.

Appendix C

Variability of the metrics over the years

We show the average of temperature, d , θ and $R\theta$, with their respective yearly difference between the maximum and the minimum occurrences of that year in Figure C.1. T has units of degrees Celsius, while the metrics take relative values, as they have been rescaled by dividing by their respective mean of the full series.

Averages and differences are taken over each year :

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{x}_n &= \frac{1}{x} \frac{1}{365} \sum_{i=n365+1}^{n365+365} x_i \\ \sigma_n &= \frac{\max(x_n) - \min(x_n)}{2}\end{aligned}\tag{C.1}$$

for $\{n \in \mathbb{N}_0 : 0 \leq n \leq 41\}$.

We see a slight decrease of the differences σ_n of d until 2002 and another slight increase until 2020, which corresponds to the one observed in R . θ and σ_n also appear to change from 2002 on. The biggest and clearer trend is the increase of temperature over the years, reflecting the global warming, with linear regression pointing to an increase of $1.5 \pm 0.2^\circ C$ over the 42 years.

C. VARIABILITY OF THE METRICS OVER THE YEARS

Figure C.1: Yearly means of d , θ and R by (C.1), the dotted lines correspond to $\bar{x}_n \pm \sigma_n$ of year n . We see the increase of temperature, reflecting the global warming, with an increase of $1.5 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ over the 42 years. The other quantities do not exhibit major trends.

Appendix D

Extremes of α

We selected the 10 days with smallest α and the 10 days with biggest α , together with the respective values of the other metrics. Besides verifying again the tendency for lower (higher) α to associate with higher (lower) codimension, we find that low α 's tend to associate with big R_{co} 's, and high α 's with small θ_{co} (Figure D.1). Lower θ_{co} mean stable orbit recurrences (only if not associated to bigger R_{co}) with many consecutive days inside ball B_{biv} . The 2 groups tend to split around the mean of d_{co} and R_{co} but mostly are under the average θ_{co} (meaning a bigger than average mean cluster size). Days with small α 's tend to have higher d_{co} and bigger R_{co} while days with high α 's have lower d_{co} , and smaller θ_{co} and R_{co} (meaning slower orbit speed in phase space).

Figure D.1: Yellow circles highlight the 10 smallest values of α and their respective signatures, whereas red circles highlight the 10 biggest values of α and respective signatures.

Appendix E

Extra plots

Figure E.1: Plot of the trajectory with respect to d , θ and radius, R , of ball B . Color bar corresponds to the respective timestep i .

Figure E.2: 42 years of wind magnitudes, from January 1979 to December 2020, for $q = 0.96$. Only first 10 years of time series were plotted for better visibility. We observe much less seasonality than for temperatures 3.5.

E. EXTRA PLOTS

Figure E.3: Maximized sign concordance for temperature with season 1 from 15/03-13/09, and season 2 from 14/09-14/03.

Figure E.4: Results for fixed 6 month seasons of sign concordance as a function of start of season 1. d and θ have opposite phases. It doesn't really make sense to split the year in seasons of positively and negatively related anomalies for wind magnitudes. Figure E.5 suggests the same.

Figure E.5: Sign concordance with varying season duration. On top, we can say that sign concordance of anomalies (W, d) is not divided in seasons, with only a few exceptions, like in 1988. Anomalies of d always evolve in opposition to those of W . At the bottom, sign concordance of anomalies divided in seasons (W, θ) still holds, with a big variability of season duration, no clear pattern emerges.

E. EXTRA PLOTS

Figure E.6: On top, yearly sign concordance of anomalies of (W, d) and $(W, R\theta)$. At the bottom, same thing with threshold excluding anomalies which absolute value smaller than $\sigma/2 = 0.5$.

Year	Start sem.1 (d)	Start sem.2 (d)	Start sem.1 (θ)	Start sem.2 (θ)
1979	04_05	10_28	03_22	11_13
1980	03_10	11_16	02_21	11_14
1981	03_12	12_16	03_01	11_27
1982	04_15	11_05	03_02	11_18
1983	04_05	11_28	03_18	09_28
1984	03_27	11_14	03_12	11_12
1985	03_29	11_07	03_06	11_19
1986	04_10	11_14	02_27	11_16
1987	04_11	11_06	02_28	11_20
1988	02_29	11_26	03_06	11_18
1989	02_20	12_22	03_04	11_20
1990	02_21	10_24	03_07	11_19
1991	02_20	10_12	03_08	11_07
1992	03_01	10_24	03_02	11_08
1993	03_01	11_21	03_04	11_09
1994	02_28	11_14	03_03	11_26
1995	03_04	11_23	03_01	11_21
1996	02_27	11_13	03_01	11_13
1997	02_26	11_02	03_01	10_06
1998	02_13	11_13	03_05	10_04
1999	02_22	10_27	03_06	11_18
2000	02_29	10_26	03_04	11_06
2001	03_01	10_07	03_04	09_28
2002	03_03	10_06	03_05	10_29
2003	03_05	11_21	03_04	11_08
2004	03_04	11_21	03_04	11_15
2005	03_06	11_16	03_06	09_16
2006	03_07	11_26	03_03	11_13
2007	03_04	11_20	03_04	11_13
2008	03_07	11_24	03_01	11_14
2009	02_25	11_17	03_10	09_29
2010	03_03	11_25	03_11	11_20
2011	03_04	10_31	03_06	11_08
2012	03_13	11_09	03_01	11_13
2013	03_03	10_02	03_02	11_20
2014	03_04	11_02	03_03	11_06
2015	03_12	11_10	03_04	11_21
2016	03_08	11_02	03_03	11_08
2017	03_07	11_20	03_05	11_21
2018	03_21	11_18	02_21	11_18
2019	02_14	12_21	03_01	09_14

Table E.1: Temperature: start of seasons 1 and 2 for each year and each metric d and θ .

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